

22RPT04 RFMicrowave2

D5: Best practice guide on the calibration of antennas in different set ups including (i) different types of calibration methods, (ii) the uncertainty budget and overall uncertainty calculations and (iii) instrumentation and different calibration sites and their impact

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1. Scope

This document is written within the scope of the EPM project “RFMicrowave2” (22RPT04) and is a result of the combined experiences from CMI, PTB, RISE, SIQ and TÜBİTAK UME. It treats antenna calibrations at frequencies ranging from 9 kHz up to 40 GHz. Different antennas are calibrated in their own unique way, depending on their intended use. The intention of this best practice guide is not only to give the reader an overview of existing calibration, but it can also be used to give advice and recommendations on how to improve already existing calibrations, on improving the measurement uncertainty and show on the requirements needed to build a new site.

Special focus is on antenna calibrations for EMC testing, as this is one of the most common requests for antenna calibrations. However, most of the methods and possible improvements are applicable also for other types of antenna calibrations.

There are also calibrations for antennas which are used for different site validations. These calibrations are often a combination of factors, for instance antenna factors of two antennas and the attenuation between them. These calibrations are usually specified for a standard and the details can be found there, but they are not treated in this guide.

2. Introduction

Antenna calibration can be done in several different ways, and good antenna calibration depends on several factors. It naturally depends on the antenna, its characteristics and its intended use, but it also depends on the method, the frequency range, the antenna calibration site and its instrumentation and the accuracy required of the calibration. The latter will be in the form of the uncertainty associated with its calibration. Which type of calibration that is required depends on the intended use of the antenna. It is not uncommon for an antenna to be calibrated in several different ways, for it to be used according to several different standards.

A calibration with a low uncertainty will impose requirements on all the previous mentioned factors. In this guide typical measurement uncertainty calculations are included for several different calibration methods. These uncertainties are not to be seen as absolute but instead are to serve two purposes. The first is to show “typical” uncertainties that are present for a specific calibration method, and the second is to show typical values for a specific contribution. These values are usually not the same for different entities that perform calibrations. For instance, the same type of calibration site can have small variations in their design, which will affect the site’s uncertainty contribution.

Traceability is treated as a core metrological requirement throughout the document. For the described methods, different traceability chains and input factors are needed, for instance dimensional measurements, impedance measurements, VNA and receiver-based electrical measurements, and reference standards maintained within accredited calibration frameworks. This ensures that the resulting antenna factors are supported by an unbroken chain of measurements to recognized standards and are suitable for use in accredited EMC and antenna calibration activities.

3. Different types of calibration

The calibration of an antenna can be done with several different methods. Some of these methods are unique for a specific type of antennas, for instance the ECSM for Monopole antennas (described in a later chapter), while some methods are applicable to different types of antennas. Before going into more details about the different types of calibrations, the reader is to be cautioned that the same term for a calibration method is sometimes used for methods which are quite different. Worse, they might not even produce the same result. A most telling example is the use of the term Three-Antenna Method. It is used in both the standards CISPR 16-1-6 [4] and SAE ARP 958 rev E [6], however with completely different results. This is due to that the setup and “how to do the calibration” is different, which can be seen in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Biconical antenna calibrated with different Three-antenna methods (TAM)

The CISPR 16-1-6 [4] gives the Free-space Gain while the SAE ARP 958 [6] gives what they call the 1-m gain. This latter has significant coupling between the antennas in the calibration, but also from the ground plane, resulting in a difference in gain depending on the polarization. The intended use of the calibrated antenna should set the exact type of calibration used.

Some common calibration methods are:

- **Three antenna Method (TAM).** As it sounds, this method uses three antennas for calibration, the Antenna Under Calibration (AUC) + two additional antennas. All three-antenna methods use a defined setup to measure the attenuation between each antenna pairing, two in turn. This eventually gives system with three unknown antenna gains and three measurements, making it possible to treat like an equation system and solve for each gain. The major advantage of this method is that all three antennas can be treated as unknown. It is however recommended that one antenna has a previously known calibration, for comparison.
- **Standard Site Method (SSM).** This is basically a three-antenna method as it is defined in the calibration standard ANSI C63.5 (2017) [3]. There are differences in setup and in how to conduct the measurements depending on whether the frequency is above or below 1 GHz.
- **Standard Antenna Method (SAM).** This method is done by first measuring the attenuation between a transmitting antenna and the standard antenna (STA). The standard antenna is then replaced by the antenna under calibration (AUC). The difference in attenuation is also the difference in gain between the AUC and STA. The major advantage of this method is that i) the standard antenna can be traceably calibrated at an NMI, and ii) small reflections from for instance masts and calibration site, are likely to affect both measurements thereby cancelling themselves. This can be considered when setting requirements for site validation. However, for accuracy the STA and the AUC need to be of the same kind, for instance both being horn antennas, preferably being even of the same make and model. The number of STA for a calibration lab can thus be quite high, which can be impractical.

- **Reference Antenna method (RAM).** This method is pretty much the same as SAM. The main difference is that it has much more defined requirements on the reference/standard antenna used. For instance, ANSI C63.5 [3] requires the Reference antenna to be calculable and that the AF has been validated.

Regardless of the type of antenna that is to be calibrated and with which method, there are a few controls that should be done prior to any calibration:

- Visual inspection. Inspect the antenna for any loose or parts bent in a way not intended to. Check the connector for any signs of dirt or damage to the threading. Also check the center connector for visible defects.
- Measurement of pin depth. Inspect and measure the center pin. A protruding pin can damage other measurement equipment. Also check that the center pin is securely fixed, otherwise there can be repeatability problems.
- Measurement of the reflection coefficient. For EMC antennas this is often a requirement within the EMC test standards. But it is recommended that a measurement of the s_{11} of the antenna is measured regardless of whether it is a formal requirement, as that gives early detections of any malfunction.

4. Different calibration sites

Several different types of sites exist for antenna calibrations. The type of site needed depends on i) which type of antenna is to be calibrated, ii) which frequency range the antenna is to be calibrated in and iii) if it is to be calibrated according to a specific standard. Many EMC standards require the antennas to be calibrated according to a specific standard. They all have in common that the calibration is to be traceable back to an NMI.

Many EMC calibration standards also state which type of site(s) are required to use for a specific frequency range. They can also set requirements on each individual site, which might not be the same in different standards.

All different sites have in common that they want a well-defined calibration area free of disturbances from either signals or reflecting objects. However, this is not entirely possible, as for instance masts, stands and cables need to be used, and their influences are influenced by the radiated fields. Advice on how to minimize these influences is given for each different site.

4.1 Open Area Test Site

With the rapid development of technology, the demand for Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) tests has increased, as the electronic devices used in military, commercial, and aviation areas must comply with EMC requirements defined in national or international standards. One of the tests in the international standards is the radiated emission test performed at Semi Anechoic Chamber (SAC), Open Area Test Site (OATS), or Fully Anechoic Room (FAR) over the frequency range of 30 MHz-6 GHz by using polarized antennas, which are bilog, biconical, log-periodic and horn antennas. The receiving antennas used in the radiated emission tests shall be calibrated with low uncertainty value in order for test laboratories to declare the uncertainty in EMC test reports, including the radiated emission test results. The effects of electromagnetic fields emitted from RADARs, GSM base stations, and TV transmitters on human health shall be accurately measured in accordance with standards and the measurement results should be compared with the relevant limits. In addition, some antennas defined in CISPR 16-1-4 [10] are also used for determining the test site quality, which includes Normalized Site Attenuation (NSA) of the SAC and the OATS, where NSA is measured using two calibrated antennas to characterize the test site performance. Therefore, the Antenna Factor (AF) of the antennas used in EMC tests, electromagnetic pollution and NSA measurements shall be measured precisely and low uncertainty value in the frequency range of 30 MHz – 1 GHz in accordance with internationally recognized standards, i.e. CISPR 16-1-6 [4] or ANSI C63.5 [3].

The ideal Open Area Test Site (OATS) is defined as a perfectly flat, infinitely large, continuous ground plane having infinite conductivity and located in free space. The term “free space” is defined as an open area, free of objects that can reflect electromagnetic waves, including buildings, electric lines, fences, trees, hills, etc. Obviously, there are no sites in the world that are “ideal” since most OATS will have some degree of imperfection, although most sites strive to be as near as ideal as possible.

The typical OATS is composed of a ground plane, an antenna mast, and a non-metallic control room located above or below the ground plane. In addition, the antenna calibration system includes a spectrum analyzer, an RF signal generator, a network analyzer, and other auxiliary equipment.

Figure 2: Antenna calibration setup

After the construction of an OATS, Normalized Site Attenuation (NSA) and Site Insertion Loss (SIL) measurements should be performed as per ANSI C63.4 [11] and CISPR 16-1-5 [12] for the validation using calculable half-wave resonant dipole antennas. To mention some additional requirements about the structure and Fundamentals of the Open Area Test Site (OATS); unwanted reflective objects within the test volume and surrounding area should be avoided. A field antenna used for product measurements shouldn't be used for measurements. Temperature changes during measurements should be less than 5 °C. Low ambient levels are recommended to achieve the recommended 16 dB, signal-to-noise ratio. NSA deviations shall remain within the tolerance limits defined in CISPR 16-1-4 [10]. There should be no protective coating against weather conditions in the antenna calibration area for frequencies of 1 GHz and below. Metal should be used on the ground plane, and there should be no holes or gaps larger than 3 cm. ($\lambda/10$, for 1 GHz). The ground plane should be electrically continuous and flat (± 3 cm).

Ideally, there should be no ambient signals, for instance FM radio, mobile backhaul and so on. In practice that is virtually impossible to achieve. Therefore, it is recommended to do a background signal check. Use a setup consisting of an antenna and signal receiver, for instance a spectrum analyzer to measure which signals are present. The direction from which the signals are coming from can be hard to pinpoint, so omnidirectional antennas like biconical and/or dipole antennas are preferred. This is to be done in both horizontal and vertical polarization.

The influence from these background signals should be minimized as far as possible, for antenna calibrations as well as for site validation. One way of accomplishing this can be to increase the number of frequency points measured. If a signal is present at a specific frequency, the two adjacent frequency points can be used to do a linear extrapolation for the "disturbed" frequency point. It is recommended that each adjacent frequency point is no more than required stepsize/2 MHz apart from the disturbed frequency point.

A comment on statistical site verification; The standard deviation must be calculated for each frequency value in measurements taken at 5 different locations. The following standard deviation values must be provided for the antenna calibration field; for horizontal polarization, maximum 0.3 dB, for vertical polarization, maximum 0.6 dB.

Figure 3: Sample graph showing standard deviation values for measurements taken at 5 different locations with horizontal polarization (R= 10 m, Tx antenna 2 m)

The dual antenna factor is the sum of the factors of two pairs of antennas. The dual antenna factor is obtained from the theoretical NSA value. Another key point is the Geometry Specific Correction Factor (GSCF). The correction factor (dB) is calculated or measured for each frequency value in the specific measurement geometry. It is obtained from the GSCF site attenuation.

According to the C63.5-2017 [3]:

$$AF_1 + AF_2 = A_1 + 20 \cdot \log f_M - 48.92 + E_D^{max} \tag{1}$$

AF₁, AF₂: Antenna factors of transmitting and receiving antennas.

A₁ : Site attenuation

f_M : Frequency (MHz)

E_D^{max} : Defined as in C63.5-2017 [3]

$$DAF = AF_1 + AF_2 \tag{2}$$

$$DAF = A_1 + 20 \cdot \log f_M - 48.92 + E_D^{max} \tag{3}$$

Specific Geometry (GS)

$$DAF_{GS} = A_{GS} + 20 \cdot \log f_M - 48.92 + E_{DGS}^{max} \tag{4}$$

Near Free Space Geometry (NFSG)

$$DAF_{NFSG} = A_{NFSG} + 20 \cdot \log f_M - 48.92 + E_{DNFSG}^{max} \tag{5}$$

GSCF, from the ANSI C63.5-2017 [3]

$$GSCF = (E_{DGS}^{max} + A_{GS}) - (E_{DNFGS}^{max} + A_{NFGS}) \tag{6}$$

E_D^{max} calculation from ANSI C63.5-2017 [3] (For horizontal polarization 30 MHz- 1 GHz)

$$E_{DH}^{max} = \frac{\sqrt{49,2\{d_2^2 + d_1^2|\rho_h|^2 + 2d_1d_2|\rho_h|\cos[\phi_h - \beta(d_2 - d_1)]\}}}{d_1d_2} \tag{7}$$

$$h_2^{min} \leq h_2 \leq h_2^{max} \tag{8}$$

$$d_1 = [R^2 + (h_1 - h_2)^2]^{1/2} \tag{9}$$

$$d_2 = [R^2 + (h_1 + h_2)^2]^{1/2} \tag{10}$$

$$\rho_h = \frac{\sin \gamma - (K - j60\lambda\sigma - \cos^2 \gamma)^{1/2}}{\sin \gamma + (K - j60\lambda\sigma - \cos^2 \gamma)^{1/2}} \tag{11}$$

$$\gamma = \arctan\left(\frac{h_1 + h_2}{R}\right) \tag{12}$$

$$E_{dB} = 20 \log E \tag{13}$$

K: Relative permittivity of the ground

σ : Conductivity of the ground (S/m)

γ : Reflection angle

ϕ : Phase angle of the reflection coefficient

β : $2\pi/\lambda$

λ : Wavelength (m)

Figure 4: SSM measurement geometry (30 MHz – 1 GHz)

For 30 MHz – 1 GHz frequency range:

$$E_{DV}^{max} = \frac{\sqrt{49.2}R^2 \{d_2^6 + d_1^6 |\rho_h|^2 + 2d_1^3 d_2^3 |\rho_V| \cos[\phi_V - \beta(d_2 - d_1)]\}^{1/2}}{d_1^3 d_2^3} \quad (14)$$

$$\rho_V = \frac{(K - j60\lambda\sigma) \sin \gamma - (K - j60\lambda\sigma - \cos^2 \gamma)^{1/2}}{(K - j60\lambda\sigma) \sin \gamma + (K - j60\lambda\sigma - \cos^2 \gamma)^{1/2}} \quad (15)$$

For 1 GHz – 40 GHz frequency range:

$$E_D^{max} = 10 \log 49.2 - 20 \log R = 16.9 - 20 \log R \left(\frac{dBuV}{m} \right) \quad (16)$$

Figure 5: Open area test site at TÜBİTAK UME

4.2 Semi-Anechoic Chamber Architectures (SAC)

A semi-anechoic chamber is one of the most critical test environments used in antenna calibrations. These chambers are based on the principle of a shielded room to block electromagnetic interference from the external environment, while a large portion of their interior surfaces are covered with special RF absorber materials that absorb electromagnetic waves. This allows the signals generated between the antennas to be measured under conditions that are as close as possible to free space conditions within the chamber. The chambers are designed to carry out tests in the 30 Hz – 40 GHz frequency range.

The key difference with semi-anechoic chambers is that their floors are left reflective. This provides a significant advantage, particularly in antenna calibrations and in achieving conditions closer to real-world usage scenarios. Structurally, the chambers consist of metal shielding panels, RF absorbing pyramids, controlled access doors and power line filters. This ensures electromagnetic isolation and minimizes wave reflections thereby increasing the accuracy of the calibration. One of the most important factors determining the performance of semi-anechoic chambers is the RF absorber materials used. These materials, typically designed in pyramid or wedge shapes, ensure that electromagnetic waves are absorbed across a wide frequency range. This prevents the waves from reflecting off the chamber's interior surfaces,

thereby improving measurement accuracy. The thickness, shape, and placement density of the absorber materials directly affect the attenuation performance of the chamber at different frequencies. This is to better simulate the real-world operating conditions of the devices. In antenna calibrations, floor reflection is important for predicting how devices will behave in real environments.

A reflective floor allows for simultaneous measurement of the direct path and reflected path components between the antennas. This ensures that calibration results reflect not only ideal conditions but also practical scenarios.

Figure 6: Antenna calibration setup in SAC

Some of the benefits can be summarized as follows:

- Minimized reflected electromagnetic waves.
- Provides high attenuation across a wide frequency range.
- Increasing the repeatability of tests.
- Simulates real-world usage scenarios more accurately.
- Measures both direct and reflected paths in antenna calibrations.

The validity of the results data is directly dependent on the periodic calibration of the chamber and setup (cable routing, common grounding, field instrumentation); therefore, the chamber itself should be treated as a “measurement site” and monitored with regular verifications. The performance of a semi-anechoic chamber is defined by the frequency range it covers and the attenuation (reflection suppression) it provides within that range. In practice, suppressing wall/ceiling reflections becomes difficult at low frequencies (below VHF) because the wavelength increases; ferrite tiles are effective absorbers in this region. At mid-to-high frequencies (VHF-SHF), pyramid/wedge-shaped polyurethane absorbers deliver superior performance. Hybrid approaches (ferrite+ pyramid) provide wideband coverage, enabling consistent reflection suppression from 30 MHz - 40 GHz. The accuracy of measurements depends not only on absorber quality but also on room dimensions, test distance (3 m / 10 m), antenna alignment, cable routing, and the geometry of the floor reflector area. At high frequencies, “field modes” and “standing waves” within the chamber become critical; therefore, layout ensuring field homogeneity and periodic verifications are mandatory. Field metrics such as “Normalized Site Attenuation” NSA in antenna calibration measurements provide information about the wave behavior in the room. Reflection loss of the absorber material varies with frequency depending on parameters such as thickness and cone height; long pyramids give better results at high frequencies, while the continuity of the ferrite tile layout is decisive at low frequencies. To prevent the room from experiencing a decline in performance over time, the aging, displacement, and moisture effects of the absorbers must be monitored; the conductivity and connection continuity of the floor reflective panel must be maintained.

4.3 Fully Anechoic Architectures (FAR) and Differences with Semi-Anechoic (SAC) Architectures

A fully anechoic room (FAR), on the other hand, minimizes internal EM wave reflections by covering the floor with absorbers; suppressing reflection components reduces uncertainty, particularly in antenna and field probe characterizations at high frequencies. The FAR architecture can provide an accuracy advantage with a lower reflection coefficient. During the calibration process, reference antennas, field probes, and a low-uncertainty signal/power chain are used; the antenna-antenna geometry, cable routing, and electrical continuity of the floor panel are kept constant. In the calibrations, metrics such as site VSWR are measured and monitored for compliance with reference curves; deviations may indicate panel connections, absorber aging, door/vent leaks, or cable routing changes.

4.4 Validation of the Calibration Sites

4.4.1 NSA Measurements

The Normalized Site Attenuation (NSA) measurements shall be carried out in accordance with the requirements specified in CISPR 16-1-4 [1]: Specification for radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus and methods- Part 1-4: Radiated disturbance measuring antennas and test sites. Where applicable, ANSI C63.5 [3] or ANSI C63.4 [11] may be used as complementary references in 30 MHz to 1 GHz frequency range. The measured NSA at a radiated emissions test site must fall within ± 4 dB of the theoretical NSA value calculated for an ideal test site. For newly established sites or for sites that have undergone physical or electrical modifications, compliance with this acceptance criterion must be verified periodically. Subsequent validation intervals may be extended (up to three years) or shortened depending on factors such as the extent and intensity of site usage, the impact of environmental conditions, gradual changes in the reflective properties of covering structures in weather-protected OATS facilities, and any physical alterations made to the site or its surrounding areas (see ANSI C63.7 [9]). It is recommended that periodic site attenuation measurements be conducted to identify potential anomalies resulting from degradation of all-weather protective materials (e.g., moisture absorption) or contamination of enclosure materials. A 12-month interval is generally considered sufficient. The primary objective is to maintain the required measurement accuracy while achieving an optimal balance between risk and cost. Antenna heights and the separation distance shall be set exactly as defined in the applicable standard. The measurement distance shall be 3 meters or 10 meters, depending on the intended radiated emission test configuration.

Figure 7: Tübitak UME's OATS

During the NSA measurement procedure, the voltage ratio shall be determined in two steps. The initial V_r value shall be obtained by disconnecting the coaxial cables from the transmitting and receiving antennas and directly connecting the two cables to each other using an adapter. This step shall establish the reference level of the measurement system. The second V_r value shall be obtained by reconnecting the coaxial cables to the respective transmitting and receiving antennas. The receiving antenna shall be scanned over the specified height range to determine the maximum received signal amplitude. Both the transmitting and receiving antennas shall be calibrated prior to the measurements. The antenna calibration data shall be applied during the evaluation of the NSA results. The use of traceable calibration data to an NMI should be ensured to maintain the measurement traceability. The height and polarization of the transmitting antenna above the conductive ground plane shall be adjusted in accordance with the requirements specified in CISPR 16-1-4 [10]. The receiving antenna shall be mounted on a calibrated antenna mast. The polarization of the receiving antenna shall be identical to that of the transmitting antenna for each measurement. The transmitting and receiving antennas shall be selected from wideband antennas, suitable for the frequency range under test. The separation distance between the antennas shall be set in accordance with the applicable standard. Then the transmitting antenna shall be driven by a signal source located in the control room. The receiving antenna, mounted on the antenna mast shall be scanned vertically over the height range from 1 meter to 4 meters. During the antenna height scan, the amplitude of the received signal shall be monitored using an EMI test receiver in the control room and connected to the receiving antenna. The maximum signal amplitude observed during the scan shall be recorded as V_r and V_i . This measurement sequence shall be repeated for all frequencies specified in the standard and for both antenna polarizations, as applicable. Following completion of the antenna-based measurements, the transmitting and receiving antennas shall be removed from the test site. The coaxial cables previously connected to the antennas shall be directly connected to each other using a coaxial adapter. The amplitude of the signal measured by the EMI receiver shall be recorded for all frequency points. It is mandatory that the amplitude of the signal source used during the antenna measurements (i.e. when the antennas are connected) shall be identical to the amplitude of the signal source used during the reference measurement (i.e. when the antennas are removed and coaxial cables are directly connected). Any variation in the signal source level shall invalidate the NSA measurement results.

$$NSA = AN = V_{Direct} - V_{Alan} - AFT - AFR - \Delta AFTOT \quad (17)$$

$$V_{Direct} = VI - CT - CR \quad (18)$$

- AN : Measured NSA value
 AFT : Transmitter antenna factor (dB/m) (GSCF factor should be taken into account)
 AFR : Receiver antenna factor (dB/m) (GSCF factor should be taken into account)
 $\Delta AFTOT$: Common impedance correction factor (Only for 3 m measurement distance and dipoles)
 VI : Signal source amplitude value (dBm)
 CT: Amount of cable loss between the signal source and the transmitter antenna (dB)
 CR: Amount of cable loss between the receiver antenna and the EMI test receiver (dB)

The NSA value measured using the above formula is calculated. $\Delta AFTOT$ (common impedance correction factor) values are only available at a 3 m test distance and when using adjustable dipoles and are defined in the standard. For broadband antennas, $\Delta AFTOT$, values are zero and are neglected. The NSA values found are compared with the theoretical NSA values given in the standard. The parameters AFT and AFR shall be established in accordance with the antenna calibration procedures defined in ANSI C63.5 [3]. The mutual impedance correction factor, $\Delta AFTOT$, is acceptable only for a 3-meter site geometry when tuned dipole antennas are used, and it applies to both horizontal and vertical polarizations. For all other site geometries involving tuned dipoles, $\Delta AFTOT$ shall be considered zero. The appropriate Ground-Reflection Site Correction Factors (GSCF), as determined in accordance with ANSI C63.5 [3], shall also be applied. NSA measurements require the use of linearly polarized antennas with calibrated antenna factors. Antenna factors must be determined using the SSM described in ANSI C63.5 [3], and all related measurements shall be traceable to a recognized national standard. In accordance with Clause 4.4.2 of ANSI C63.5-2017 [3], antennas shall be calibrated as a pair, meaning that the transmit and receive antennas must be calibrated together. Antenna factors typically include the lossless associated with the balun. If an external balun, built-in attenuators, or both are employed, their effects must be incorporated into the antenna calibration results. The transmit and receive antennas must be identical, that is, of the same manufacturer and model number, unless individually calibrated antennas are used whose antenna factors differ by no more than 1 dB, at each calibration frequency. The NSA shall be measured in one or both of the following procedures. First is “the discrete frequency measurement method and the second one is the “swept frequency method”. The swept-

frequency measurement technique is permitted only when broadband antennas are used. However, tuned dipole antennas may be employed at discrete, fixed frequencies when spot checks or troubleshooting of NSA results are required. This allowance applies solely to understanding test sites; tuned dipoles shall not be used for NSA validation of alternative test sites. For tuned dipole antennas, figure below represents the NSA measurement configuration for horizontal polarization while one below shows corresponding configuration for vertical polarization (assuming the dipoles are properly tuned for all frequencies down to 30 MHz). To ensure a minimum separation of 25 cm between the reference ground plane and the lowest tip of both the transmit and receive antennas, specific height constraints are applied. The transmit antenna height is fixed at 2.75 m, and downward movement of the receive antenna is limited accordingly. These constraints are explicitly defined by the minimum scan-height values provided in the corresponding standard.

Figure 8: Site attenuation measurement geometry: horizontal polarization; broadband or tuned dipole antennas

Figure 9: Site attenuation measurement geometry: vertical polarization using tuned dipole antennas

For alternative test sites such as weather protected OATS or a semi anechoic chamber a single position NSA measurement is not adequate to detect potential reflections caused by structural elements, RF absorbing wall and ceiling materials, or weather protection coverings. A weather protected OATS, whether the protective structure covers only one part of the site (e.g. turntable area) or the entire facility, is not classified as a standard site. This is because the influence of covering structure cannot be properly assessed without conducting volumetric NSA measurements. Therefore, each weather protected OATS must be validated using the positions and geometries specified. Unlike standard tests, where single position NSA measurements are sufficient, alternative test sites require measurements at multiple, equally spaced antenna

positions on the reference ground plane. For alternative test sites, a “validated test volume” is defined as the imaginary cylindrical space swept by the largest equipment under test as it rotates 360 ° about its center (for example, on a turntable) This cylindrical region represents the volume that must be validated using the measurement positions and geometries described. During the site evaluation, the transmit antenna must be positioned at various locations within the validated test volume, using both horizontal and vertical polarizations. This process may require up to 20 individual site attenuation measurements; five horizontal plane positions (center, left, right, front, and rear defined relative to the center and a reference line extending from the center to the measuring antenna position), two antenna polarizations (horizontal and vertical), and up to two transmit antenna heights per polarization.

Figure 10: Typical antenna positions for alternative test sites: vertical polarization NSA measurements; a) perspective view, b) top view

Figure 11: Typical antenna positions for alternative test sites: horizontal polarization NSA measurements; a) perspective view, b) top view

Figure 12: Typical antenna positions for alternative test sites: vertical polarization NSA measurements for EUT that does not exceed a volume of 1.2 m diameter and 1.5 height, with the periphery greater than 1 m from the closest material that may cause undesirable reflections.

Figure 13: Typical antenna positions for alternative test sites: horizontal polarization NSA measurements for an EUT that does not exceed a volume of 1.2 m diameter and 1.5 m height, with the periphery greater than 1 m from the closest material that may cause undesirable reflections.

Model function related to performing NSA calibration using an EMI Receiver & Spectrum Analyzer and Signal Source:

$$NSA = GNSA + U_A^{SpA} + U_f^{SpA} + U_f^{no-prescan} + U_A^{SS} + U_f^{SG} + U_G^{AMP} + U_L^{Cables} + U_{VSWR}^{XMT} + U_{VSWR}^{RCV} + U^{phase\ center} + U^{directivity} + U^{pattern} + Ah + Ad + Mc + A_F + A_I + U_{rept}, \tag{19}$$

Model function for performing NSA calibration using NA

$$NSA = GNSA + U_A^{NA} + U_L^{NA} + U_L^{Cables} + U_{VSWR}^{XMT} + U_{VSWR}^{RCV} + U^{phase\ center} + U^{directivity} + U^{pattern} + Ah + Ad + Mc + A_F + A_I + U_{rept}, \tag{20}$$

Uncertainty budget of the NSA measurements

Component Symbol	Component Name	Unit	Definition
NSA	Signal source amplitude sensitivity	dB/m	This is the measured value, i.e., the result.
GNSA	Signal source frequency sensitivity	dB/m	It is obtained by subtracting the normalization value measured by the EMI Receiver & Spectrum Analyzer & Network Analyzer from the site attenuation value measured by the same devices, the transmitter and receiver antenna factors, and the common impedance correction factor.
U_A^{SpA}	Amplifier gain stability	dB	Uncertainty arising from the amplitude sensitivity of the spectrum analyzer
U_f^{SpA}	Cable loss variations	dB	Uncertainty arising from the frequency range (span) sensitivity of the spectrum analyzer
$U_f^{no-prescan}$	Transmitter section impedance mismatch	dB	Uncertainty arising from the frequency sensitivity of the “Discrete” frequency method without pre-scanning
U_A^{SS}	Receiver section impedance mismatch	dB	Uncertainty arising from the amplitude sensitivity of the signal source
U_f^{SG}	Changes in the phase center of the antenna	dB	Uncertainty arising from the frequency sensitivity of the signal source

U_{G}^{AMP}	Antenna directivity	dB	Uncertainty arising from the non-constant gain of the amplifier, if one is used
U_{L}^{Cables}	Difference between the transmitter pattern and the dipole	dB	Uncertainty arising from the change in cable loss value due to effects such as temperature, humidity, etc.
U_{VSWR}^{XMT}	Antenna height	dB	Uncertainty arising from impedance mismatch in the transmitter section
U_{VSWR}^{RCV}	Measurement distance	dB	Uncertainty arising from impedance mismatch in the receiver section
$U_{phase\ center}$	Interaction between antennas	dB	Uncertainty arising from the non-constant phase center of the antenna
$U_{directivity}$	Antenna factor	dB	Uncertainty arising from antenna directivity
$U_{pattern}$	Antenna factor combination	dB	Uncertainty arising from the transmitter pattern differing from the dipole
Ah	Repeatability	dB	Error arising from the unwanted interaction of the antenna with the metal surface
Ad	Network analyzer amplitude sensitivity	dB	Mutual coupling between antennas arising from the measurement distance
Mc	Network analyzer linearity	dB	Uncertainty arising from interaction between antennas (reflection, coupling, etc.)
A_F	Signal source amplitude sensitivity	dB	Uncertainty arising from the antenna factor.
A_I	Signal source frequency sensitivity	dB	Uncertainty arising from the combination process performed when finding the antenna factor
$U_{rept.}$	Amplifier gain stability	dB	Determined from the standard deviation derived from 10 consecutive measurement results
U_A^{NA}	Cable loss variations	dB	Uncertainty arising from the amplitude sensitivity of the network analyzer
U_L^{NA}	Transmitter section impedance mismatch	dB	Uncertainty arising from the non-linearity of the network analyzer

Table 1: Uncertainty budget for NSA measurements

4.4.2 SIL Measurement

Site insertion loss (SIL) is defined as:

$$SIL = 10 \log_{10} \frac{P_1}{P_2} \text{ dB} \quad (21)$$

Where P_1 is the power accepted by the receiver when the coaxial cables including the matching pads are connected directly, and P_2 is the power accepted when the signal is transmitted from one antenna to the other across a measurement site.

Site insertion loss (SIL) measurements are performed to validate the antenna calibration sites as per CISPR 16-1-5 [12] within the scope of CALTS and REFTS (limits for CALTS and REFTS are 1.0 dB, 1.5 dB respectively) by using calculable dipole antennas. The validation process first requires the production of theoretical SIL values based on dimensions of dipole antennas employed, three-port balun S-parameters, the condition of the ground floor, and measurement geometry such as antenna heights, measurement distance and polarization.

Figure 14: Example photo of the SIL measurement

$$|SIL_m - SIL_c| < T_{SIL} - \Delta SIL_m \quad (22)$$

- SIL_m is measured according to CALTS and REFTS
- SIL_c is calculated according to CALTS and REFTS
- T_{SIL} is the allowed tolerance in SIL, in dB,
- ΔSIL_m is the SIL measurement uncertainty (k=2), in dB.

Uncertainty calculations shall be performed to evaluate whether the SIL measurement results comply with the limits in the CISPR 16-1-5 [12] standard. The SIL measurements were carried out in different twelve frequency bands using calculable dipole antennas of different sizes for HP and VP at 30 MHz – 1000 MHz frequency range. As a result of the measurements performed, uncertainty budgets were calculated separately for each band. SIL_m are strongly affected by various parameters influencing the voltage measurements. Therefore, it is extremely important to create the model function for SIL measurements.

$$SIL_m = (V_D + \delta_{M1}) - (V_S + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_{AN} + \delta_P) + \delta_C \quad (23)$$

V_D and V_S represent the important effects of the network analyzer dynamic accuracy for direct connection of cables and connections cables to antennas respectively. Uncertainties due to dynamic accuracy are taken from the data sheet of the network analyzer. The other important effects are mismatches. These are given by δ_{M1} , δ_{M2} and δ_{M3} . δ_{M1} is the mismatch effect measured by directly connecting the receiver and transmitter antenna cables with attenuators. δ_{M2} and δ_{M3} are the mismatch effects of transmitter and receiver antenna cables with attenuators were measured separately. In order to determine the mismatches. Standing Wave Ratio (SWR) measurements were performed with the network analyzer. Then, the reflection coefficients were calculated depending on the frequency using Equation below

$$|r| = \frac{SWR - 1}{SWR + 1} \quad (24)$$

Then using the reflection coefficients, the mismatch values were calculated depending on the frequency using equation below

$$Mismatch [dB] = 20 \cdot \log(1 \pm r^2) \quad (25)$$

δ_C is cable attenuation variation due to the cable flexing or temperature fluctuation. For this purpose, measurements were carried out at a temperature difference of three degrees in the morning and afternoon. δ_{AN} is the uncertainty due to the effect of ambient noise and δ_P is the uncertainty due to antenna height during SIL measurements. Antenna position measurements were performed at ± 1 cm height differences of the receiver antenna. Especially the error originating from antenna positions has a height effect on uncertainty. For this reason, antenna heights should be taken into consideration during measurements and should be adjusted precisely.

Figure 15: Example photo of the SIL measurement

Uncertainty components and example values are given in Table 2 below. All the components have a sensitivity coefficient of unity.

Uncertainty budget of the SIL measurement

Source of uncertainty / Symbol	Probability distribution / Divisor
Receiver reading after direct connection of cables / V_D	Rectangular / $\sqrt{3}$
Receiver reading after connecting cables to antennas / V_S	Rectangular / $\sqrt{3}$
Generator-receiver (direct connection mismatch with an adapter) / δ_{M1}	U-shaped / $\sqrt{2}$
Generator-antenna mismatch / δ_{M2}	U-shaped / $\sqrt{2}$
Antenna-receiver mismatch / δ_{M3}	U-shaped / $\sqrt{2}$
Cable attenuation variation due to cable flexing or temperature fluctuation / δ_C	Rectangular / $\sqrt{3}$
Ambient noise / δ_{AN}	Rectangular / $\sqrt{3}$

Antenna positioning / δ_p	Rectangular / $\sqrt{3}$
-------------------------------------	-----------------------------

Table 2: Uncertainty budget for SIL measurements

4.4.3 VSWR Measurement

To ensure illumination of all reflective surfaces during this test and to simulate potential low directional antenna gains, the antenna used as the transmission source must be linearly polarized and have a dipole-like radiation pattern with the following detailed specifications. Radiation pattern data must be available with a frequency step size less than or equal to 1 GHz. A field validation test is performed for cylindrical volume. The base of the cylinder is determined by the surface used to support the antenna. The top of the cylinder is selected as the maximum height that an antenna and its vertical overhead cables will cover. The diameter of the cylinder is the largest diameter required to accommodate an antenna, including cables. The S_{VSWR} is evaluated by placing the receiving antenna where the volume is to be validated and changing the transmitter source location between defined locations. Alternatively, using the S_{VSWR} procedure, the locations described in this subsection are used for the placement of the field probe in the test volume. The locations required for making S_{VSWR} measurements depend on the dimensions of the calibration volume. For each required location and polarization, S_{VSWR} is evaluated with six measurement sequences along a line leading to the reference point of the receiving antenna. The six measurement sequences along the line to the receiving antenna are shown with points in Figure XX.

Figure 16: Site voltage wave standing wave ratio measurement points

A test site shall be considered acceptable for radiated electromagnetic field measurements in 1 GHz to 18 GHz if it satisfies the criterion provided in CISPR 16-1-4 [10] site validation procedure. Test sites used for measurements in 1 GHz to 18 GHz shall have a design that minimizes the influence of reflections upon the received signal, for example an anechoic chamber. If the site is not designed to provide fully anechoic conditions, for example a semi-anechoic chamber, use of absorbing material to cover part of the metal ground plane is required. Site validation is performed by measurements of the so-called site voltage standing wave ratio (S_{VSWR}). The site validation method evaluates a given test volume for the specific combination of site, receive antenna, test distance (described in CISPR 16-2-3 [13]), and absorbing material placed on the ground plane, if needed to meet the criterion of 8.3.2. Influences of the receive antenna must be located as used for the site validation tests, and permanently fixed objects in the test volume (such as a permanently installed turntable), are evaluated by and included in this site validation procedure. Removable objects, such as a removable test table, are not required to be in place during the site validation tests. The S_{VSWR} is the ratio of maximum received signal to minimum received signal, caused by interference between direct (intended) and reflected signals, or

$$S_{VSWR} = \frac{E_{Max}}{E_{Min}} = \frac{V_{Max}}{V_{Min}} \quad (26)$$

$$= 20 \text{Log} \left(\frac{E_{Max}}{E_{Min}} \right) = 20 \text{Log} \left(\frac{V_{Max}}{V_{Min}} \right) = V_{Max} - V_{Min} = E_{Max} - E_{Min} \quad (27)$$

The S_{VSWR} is directly related to influences of undesired reflections. The acceptance criterion for 1 GHz to 18 GHz site validations is

$$S_{VSWR,dB} = 6 \text{ dB} \quad (28)$$

5. Low frequency antenna calibration (≤ 30 MHz)

Chapter 5 deals with low-frequency calibration of antennas in particular monopole antennas (Chapter 5.1) and loop antennas (Chapter 5.2). In this chapter only a short overview is given. More detailed explanation can be found in the “RF Microwave 2” deliverable D3 entitled “*Improved calibration method for the calibration of monopole antennas by the equivalent capacitance substitution method (ECSM) and loop antennas by TAM and Helmholtz coils*” [14].

5.1 Monopole antennas

Monopole antennas are widely used for low-frequency EMC measurements, typically in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz, and for some antenna models up to 100 MHz. A practical monopole antenna usually consists of a vertical rod and a matching unit, where the matching unit provides the electrical interface to the receiver and may contain passive matching circuits or an amplifier. The electrical contact between the matching unit and the ground plane is very important because it directly affects repeatability and the resulting antenna factor.

At low frequencies, conventional far-field calibration methods are difficult to apply because the wavelengths are very long and the required test distances become impractical. For this reason, monopole antennas are commonly calibrated either by the plane-wave method or by the Equivalent Capacitance Substitution Method (ECSM). This chapter focuses on ECSM as a practical and traceable laboratory method for short monopole antennas, while also noting that the plane-wave method is necessary when the actual installation geometry cannot be represented well by capacitance substitution.

The main calibrated quantity is the antenna factor AF , which relates the incident electric field strength to the voltage measured at the antenna output. In EMC practice, the calibrated AF must correspond to the actual conditions of use, including rod length, ground plane arrangement, cable connection, and the physical position of the matching unit. This is especially important for monopole antennas that are used with a counterpoise or on a tripod, since their AF can differ significantly from the value obtained with the matching unit mounted directly on a large conductive ground plane.

5.1.1 Equivalent Capacitance Substitution Method (ECSM)

Theoretical Basis

The Equivalent Capacitance Substitution Method is based on replacing the monopole rod by a capacitor that has the same self-capacitance as the rod above an ideal ground plane. Instead of exposing the antenna to a known plane wave, the matching unit is characterized electrically with this dummy capacitor attached at the antenna input. The measured electrical transfer is then converted into AF using the effective height correction.

This method is valid only for electrically short monopoles. ECSM can be used only when the total length from the base of the matching unit to the top of the rod is shorter than approximately $\lambda/8$. When the rod becomes electrically longer, the simple capacitance model becomes less accurate and the uncertainty increases. For antennas used beyond this limit, especially those specified up to 100 MHz, the plane-wave method should be used instead.

The AF of a monopole antenna is defined by Eq. 29 in linear form and by Eq. 30 in logarithmic form.

$$AF = \frac{E}{V_M} \cdot h_e \text{ (m}^{-1}\text{)} \quad (29)$$

$$AF_{dB} = V_D - V_L - L_h + \Delta U_{dB} \text{ (dB(m}^{-1}\text{))} \quad (30)$$

The E denotes the electric field strength in V/m, V_M is the voltage at the matching unit output, V_D is the measured output of the signal generator in dB(μ V), V_L is the measured output of the matching unit in dB(μ V), L_h is the height correction factor in dB(m) and ΔU_{dB} (dB) is for any resistive losses in the adapter. If the adapter is purely capacitive, ΔU_{dB} can be assumed as 0.

The height correction factor L_h in dB(m) and effective height of the rod h_e in meters are calculated using Eqs. 31 and 32.

$$L_h = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{h_e} \right) \quad (31)$$

$$h_e = \frac{h}{\pi} \tan \left(\frac{\pi h}{\lambda} \right) \quad (32)$$

The λ denotes the wavelength of the signal ($\lambda = c/f$), c is the speed of light ($2.998 \cdot 10^8$ m/s), f is the frequency of the signal, and h is the actual height (length) of the rod in meters. The effective length h_e thus expresses the relation between the voltage induced in the antenna and the vertical component of the incident electric field.

For a short cylindrical monopole, the effective height is approximately one half of the physical rod length at low frequency. If the matching unit is located above the ground plane, it contributes to the effective height and affects the measured AF . In practice, an empirical correction may be applied by adding about half the housing height to the rod length when calculating the height correction term, Eq. 33 where h_b denotes the height of the matching unit. A typical reduction of AF due to housing height is approximately 0.8 dB.

$$h_{eff} = h + \frac{h_b}{2} \quad (33)$$

The self-capacitance C_a of the dummy capacitor in pF (self-capacitance of the rod above infinite ground plane) is calculated using Eq. 34, where a denotes the average radius of the rod in meters.

$$C_a = \frac{24.2 \cdot h}{\left[\ln \left(\frac{2h}{a} \right) - 1 \right]} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\pi h}{\lambda} \right)^2}} \quad (34)$$

ECSM Adapter Design

A key element of ECSM is the dummy adapter, which must reproduce the rod capacitance as accurately as possible while introducing minimal parasitic inductance and stray capacitance, Fig. 1. The adapter consists of a small structure containing a capacitor connected between the antenna input point and the return conductor. The capacitor value should match the calculated self-capacitance of the real rod, and silver-mica capacitors with 5% tolerance are recommended because of their stability and low loss.

Figure 17: An adaptor containing dummy capacitor that is used for monopole antenna calibration with ECSM method

Several practical design rules must be followed for the adapter:

- The capacitor should be mounted in a small metal box or on a small metal frame.
- Capacitor leads should be as short as possible and should not exceed 8 mm.
- Lead spacing should typically be between 5 mm and 10 mm.
- The total lead length, including the mating connector section, should not exceed 40 mm.
- Conductive parts should remain at least 10 mm away from nearby metal surfaces to reduce unwanted capacitive coupling.
- The connector should be mounted on dielectric support and should have low inductance.
- The metallic part of the adapter should be bonded to the matching unit using a short, wide braid, typically at least 15 mm wide, to keep the return path inductance low.
- Any matching network incorporated into the dummy antenna shall be evaluated for losses and accounted for in the AF calculation.

In practice, one adapter is not sufficient for all monopole antenna geometries. Laboratories should prepare a set of ECSM adapters with different capacitance values and then choose the adapter whose calibrated capacitance most closely matches the calculated ideal capacitance of the rod under test. This is very important because a poor capacitance match can introduce large AF errors. Using 12.6 pF instead of 10 pF may result in an AF calibration error of approximately 2 dB.

Calibration Method and Instrumentation

Two ECSM calibration setups are commonly used. One uses a vector network analyzer, and the other uses a signal generator together with a measuring receiver or spectrum analyzer. In both cases, the dummy adapter is connected directly to the matching unit, and a T-connector is used so that the input drive voltage and the output voltage of the matching unit can be related.

VNA-Based Method

The VNA-based method, Fig. 18, is generally preferred for highest accuracy. The measurement procedure is as follows:

1. Connect the network analyser with the cables to be used in the measurements. A 10 dB attenuator may be connected to Port 2 of the VNA to reduce mismatch losses.
2. The length, insertion loss, and type of the cables connected between (i) the T-connector port A and the port V_D and (ii) between the 50 Ω port R and the port V_L shall be very similar (loss difference less than 0.1 dB).

Set up the matching unit to be characterized and the measuring equipment. The dummy antenna should be connected as close to the antenna port as possible, and the T-connector should be connected as close as possible to the dummy antenna.

3. Perform a 12-term error correction of the VNA at the end of the cable. This will eliminate the source and load match errors (mismatch contributions), therefore matching pads are not required.
4. Subtract the signal level V_L in dB(μ V) from the signal level V_D in dB(μ V) to obtain AF in dB(m^{-1}). If necessary (depending on the calibration adapters), subtract L_h (approximately -6 dB).

Figure 18: A measuring set-up for monopole antenna calibration with ECSM method with VNA

Signal Generator/Measuring Receiver Method

The signal-generator/measuring-receiver method, Fig. 19, is simpler in terms of instrumentation:

1. Set up the matching unit to be characterized and the measuring equipment. It is strongly recommended to use an attenuator (e.g., 10 dB) between the RF generator and T-connector to reduce mismatch.
2. With the equipment connected and a 50 Ω termination of T-connector, measure the received signal voltage V_L in dB(μ V) at the 50 Ω port R.
3. Leaving the RF output of the signal generator unchanged, transfer the 50 Ω termination to the 50 Ω port R and transfer the receiver input cable to the T-connector. Measure the drive signal voltage V_D in dB(μ V).
4. Subtract V_L from V_D to obtain AF in dB(m^{-1}).

Figure 19: A measuring set-up for monopole antenna calibration with ECSM method with signal generator and measuring receiver

Required Instrumentation

The main instruments needed for monopole calibration are:

- Vector network analyser, or RF signal generator and measuring receiver or spectrum analyser
- Precision 50 Ω termination with high return loss
- Precision coaxial cables, T-connectors, and attenuators if needed
- LCR meter for capacitance measurement at lower frequencies, typically up to about 2 MHz and Impedance analyser for capacitance measurement at higher frequencies (e.g., Keysight E4990A) to measure the capacitance of ECSM adapter
- Calibrated ruler and calliper for measuring rod length and diameter

Uncertainty Analysis

The mathematical model for ECSM calibration when measured with a VNA is defined by Eq. 7.

$$AF = \Delta V + \delta V_{\Delta, meas} + \delta V_{D, MM} + \delta V_{L, MM} + \delta V_{L, Ca} + \delta V_{L, amp} - L_h + \delta L_{L, h} \quad (35)$$

VNA Measurement Uncertainty ($\delta V_{\Delta, meas}$)

This represents the effect of VNA noise, drift, linearity, resolution, cables (reflection, attenuation, tracking symmetry) and connectors on the uncertainty of measured ΔV . This uncertainty is estimated from analysis of $|S_{21}|$ parameter calibration. Typical values for BNC and N-type connectors for different attenuations in the frequency range 9 kHz to 30 MHz are:

- 0 dB to -30 dB: 0.06 dB
- -30 dB to -50 dB: 0.08 dB
- -50 dB to -100 dB: 0.18 dB

Mismatch Uncertainty ($\delta V_{D,MM}$ and $\delta V_{L,MM}$)

The mismatch terms are calculated from Eq. 36.

$$M_D = M_L = 20 \log_{10} \left(1 + \frac{|\Gamma_M \cdot \Gamma_A \cdot \Gamma_T \cdot s_{11} \cdot s_{22} \cdot s_{21}|}{1 - |\Gamma_M \cdot s_{22}| - |\Gamma_A \cdot s_{11}|} \right) \quad (36)$$

For $\Gamma_M = \Gamma_A = \Gamma_T = 0.06$ (24 dB return loss), $s_{11} = 0.18$ (15 dB return loss), $s_{22} = 0.32$ (10 dB return loss) and $s_{21} = 1.0$, yields $M_D = M_L = 0.266$ dB. The uncertainty distribution is assumed to be U-shaped.

Capacitance Mismatch Uncertainty ($\delta V_{L,Ca}$)

This is often the dominant contribution. To estimate this uncertainty, the rod dimensions (length h and diameter $d=2a$) must be measured and the ideal capacitance C_a calculated using Eq. 6. The most appropriate ECSM adapter is then chosen from available adapters based on smallest difference. The uncertainty contribution estimated using Eq. 37. Typical values according to CISPR 16-1-6 are approximately 1.09 dB with rectangular uncertainty distribution.

$$\delta V_{L,Ca} = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{C_a}{C'_a} \right) \quad (37)$$

Effective Height Uncertainty ($\delta L_{L,h}$)

The uncertainty in effective height is estimated at 4% for rods up to 1.1 m below 35 MHz. An error of 4% in effective height causes an error of 0.34 dB in L_h with rectangular probability distribution.

Overall Uncertainty

Typical expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$, normal distribution) range from:

- 0.7 dB when calculated and measured capacitor match almost perfectly
- 1.2 dB in typical cases
- 1.7 dB when good capacitance matching cannot be achieved
-

These values demonstrate that producing a large set of different ECSM adapters is critical to obtain relatively good matching capacitors for each antenna geometry.

Traceability

Traceability in monopole antenna calibration is established through both dimensional and electrical measurement chains:

1. **Dimensional Measurements:** The rod length and diameter are measured using calibrated dimensional instruments such as a reference ruler and reference calliper. These dimensions are used to calculate the ideal self-capacitance of the rod.
2. **Capacitance Measurements:** The dummy adapter capacitance is measured with a traceably calibrated LCR meter (9 kHz to 2 MHz) or impedance analyzer (above 2 MHz). These instruments are traceable to capacitance, resistance, inductance, AC voltage, and time-base standards.
3. **RF Measurements:** The matching unit transfer is measured using a VNA or signal generator and measuring receiver. When a VNA is used, traceability is linked through calibrated open, short, load, and through standards.

In this way, the final AF is traceable to SI units through dimensional, impedance, and RF electrical quantities.

Plane-Wave Method

Although ECSM is very useful for short monopole antennas, the plane-wave method remains important. In this method, the complete monopole antenna is exposed to a known electromagnetic field above a large conductive ground plane, and the AF is determined directly from the incident field and the measured output voltage. In the plane-wave method, the entire antenna system including rod, matching unit, housing, and ground plane arrangement is illuminated by a vertically polarized plane wave. The electric field strength E at the antenna location is precisely known, and the AF is calculated using Eq. 38, where V_{out} is the voltage measured at the antenna output terminals with proper impedance matching (typically 50 Ω).

$$AF = \frac{E}{V_{out}} \quad (38)$$

The plane-wave field can be generated using:

1. **Large Open Area Test Site:** A transmitting antenna (typically biconical or log-periodic) located at a sufficient distance above a large ground plane illuminates the monopole antenna under test.
2. **GTEM Cell:** A gigahertz transverse electromagnetic cell provides a controlled plane-wave environment with known field strength derived from cell geometry and input power.

The main advantage of the plane-wave method is that it includes the complete antenna structure and surrounding geometry. This method better represents the actual use conditions when the antenna is mounted on a tripod, used with a counterpoise, or operated in a configuration that cannot be represented accurately by capacitance substitution.

The plane-wave method is mandatory for:

- Monopole antennas with total length exceeding $\lambda/8$
- Monopole antennas used on tripods or counterpoises (e.g., 0.6 m \times 0.6 m vestigial ground plates)
- Antennas specified for use up to 100 MHz where ECSM becomes inaccurate
- Verification and validation of ECSM results

The disadvantages are the need for a large and calibrated site, greater sensitivity to environmental conditions, and the difficulty of producing a well-characterized low-frequency field. For that reason, ECSM and plane-wave calibration should be regarded as complementary methods.

Conclusion

Monopole antenna calibration in the 9 kHz to 30 MHz range presents unique challenges due to long wavelengths that preclude conventional far-field methods. The plane wave method remains the reference approach but requires extensive facilities and is subject to environmental uncertainties. The Equivalent Capacitance Substitution Method (ECSM) provides a practical, laboratory-based alternative for electrically short monopoles ($h < \lambda/8$), with calibration uncertainties ranging from 0.7 dB to 1.7 dB ($k=2$) depending primarily on the quality of capacitance matching between the ideal rod capacitance and available calibration adapters.

Successful ECSM implementation requires careful attention to adapter design (minimizing parasitic inductance and capacitance), maintaining a diverse set of adapters with different capacitance values, proper measurement setup (VNA calibration, cable matching, grounding), and comprehensive uncertainty evaluation. The method's limitations must be respected: antennas exceeding $\lambda/8$, tripod-mounted configurations, and frequencies approaching resonance require plane wave calibration. When properly applied within its valid range, ECSM provides traceable, reproducible AF determination suitable for EMC compliance activities and metrology applications.

5.2 Loop antennas

5.2.1 Introduction

Loop antennas are essential measurement instruments in electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) testing for radiated disturbance measurements in the low frequency range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz. These antennas typically feature circular loop diameters up to 60 cm and are mounted on small boxes containing matching and tuning networks, with many incorporating amplifiers to enhance sensitivity. The primary calibration parameter is the magnetic field antenna factor (F_a), which relates the incident magnetic field strength to the output voltage at the antenna terminals, Eq. 39, where E defines the field strength in dB(μ V/m) of the incident plane wave and V is the resultant voltage in dB(μ V) across the 50 Ω load at the antenna output.

$$F_a = E - V \text{ [dB(m}^{-1}\text{)]} \quad (39)$$

The F_a is dependent on the load impedance, mutual coupling to surroundings, and antenna positioning relative to ground planes. When performing radiated emission measurements, the incident field strength can be calculated as $E = V + F_a$.

Well-designed loop antennas exhibit symmetry in the plane of the loop and incorporate shielding to reject electric field coupling. Poor shielding can significantly affect F_a reproducibility during calibration. Subchapter 5.2 describes four primary calibration methods for loop antennas: Three Antenna Method (TAM), reference antenna method, Helmholtz coil method, and TEM cell method. Each method has distinct advantages, limitations, uncertainty characteristics, and applicability

5.2.2 Instrumentation Requirements

Loop antenna calibration requires precision measurement instrumentation with documented traceability, Table 3. VNA calibration kits (open, short, load, thru) should be also used and calibrated at accredited laboratories.

Instrument	Application	Key Specifications
Vector Network Analyzer (VNA)	TAM, reference method	S-parameter measurements, full 2-port SOLT calibration
Signal Generator	Helmholtz, TEM cell	Stable frequency/amplitude, 9 kHz - 30 MHz range
RF Power Amplifier	TEM cell	Sufficient power for dynamic range (especially at 10 m)
RF Power Sensor	TEM cell, net power measurement	Return loss > 32 dB, traceable calibration
Digital Multimeter (DMM)	Voltage measurement Helmholtz output	50 Ω input, AC voltage capability, resolution
Precision A-meter	Helmholtz coil current measurement	Current measurement accuracy, low insertion loss
Laser Distance Meter	Antenna spacing	mm-level accuracy,

	measurement	calibration certificate
Electronic Calliper	Loop radius, dimension measurements	0.01 mm resolution, traceable to length standard
RF Attenuators (10 dB)	Mismatch reduction	Return loss > 24 dB
50 Ω Terminations	Reference loads	Return loss > 32 dB (VSWR < 1.05)

Table 3: Primary instrumentation for loop antenna calibration with traceability requirements

5.2.3 Three Antenna Method (TAM)

The Three Antenna Method (TAM) is an absolute calibration technique requiring three loop antennas measured in pairs to determine individual AF without requiring a reference standard. Unlike other methods, TAM generates an averaged magnetic field by positioning two loop antennas in parallel planes in free space, avoiding the impracticality of generating true plane waves at low frequencies. The magnetic AF s for the three antennas are calculated using Eqs. 40-42, where A_{ij} represents VNA-measured transmission S-parameters between antenna pairs, and α_{ij} are coupling factors calculated from geometric parameters.

$$AF_{m1}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{-A_{23} \alpha_{12}\alpha_{13}}{A_{12}A_{13} \alpha_{23}}} \quad (40)$$

$$AF_{m2}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{-A_{13} \alpha_{21}\alpha_{23}}{A_{21}A_{23} \alpha_{13}}} \quad (41)$$

$$AF_{m3}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{-A_{12} \alpha_{31}\alpha_{32}}{A_{31}A_{32} \alpha_{12}}} \quad (42)$$

The coupling factor between antenna pairs is defined by Eq. 43 where $k=2\cdot\pi/\lambda$ is the wave number, $\omega=2\cdot\pi\cdot f$ is angular frequency, $\mu_0=4\cdot\pi\cdot 10^{-7}$ H/m is the permeability of free space, $Z_L=50\ \Omega$ is the load impedance, r_i and r_j are loop radii. The R_{12} is defined by Eq. 44 where d_{ij} denotes the centre-to-centre distance between antenna pairs

$$\alpha_{12} = \frac{\sqrt{1+k^2R_{12}^2}}{j\omega\mu_0\pi Z_L R_{12}^3} \left[1 + \frac{15}{8} \frac{(r_1 r_2)^2}{R_{12}^4} + \frac{315}{64} \frac{(r_1 r_2)^4}{R_{12}^8} \right] \quad (43)$$

$$R_{12} = \sqrt{d_{12}^2 + r_1^2 + r_2^2} \quad (44)$$

Validity conditions: The coupling equations are valid only when both antennas are circular loops and the following constraints are satisfied, Eq. 45 and 46:

$$k \sqrt{d_{ij}^2 + r_i^2 + r_j^2} \leq 1.0 \quad (45)$$

$$\frac{r_i r_j}{d_{ij}^2 + r_i^2 + r_j^2} \leq \frac{1}{16} \quad (46)$$

Measurement Procedure

Setup requirements:

- Antennas positioned above metallic ground plane at heights between 1 m and 4 m (CISPR 16-2-3 [13])
- Antenna pairs aligned in parallel planes with centre points aligned
- Full 2-port VNA calibration (SOLT) performed at cable ends
- Alignment tolerance: centre position within ± 10 mm, angular misalignment $< 5^\circ$

Dimensional measurements:

- Measure inner loop radius r with calibrated beak scale
- Measure centre-to-centre distance d using calibrated laser distance meter plus mast diameter
- Verify alignment using laser meter for vertical axis and straight rod for horizontal axis

VNA measurements:

- Configure antenna pair in parallel orientation
- Perform S_{21} transmission measurement
- Repeat measurement, reassembling antenna pair each time to assess repeatability
- Repeat for all three antenna pairs (1-2, 2-3, 1-3)
- Calculate antenna factors using Eqs. 40-42

Uncertainty Contributions

Typical uncertainty contributions are gathered in Table 4. Combined standard uncertainty is typically between 0.6 dB and 1.0 dB ($k=2$) and is higher at lower frequencies due to increased VNA noise contribution. The dominant contributor is often S_{21} measurement uncertainty, particularly below 100 kHz where signal levels approach noise floor.

Uncertainty Source	Typical Value	Distribution
Loop radius measurement	± 3 mm	Rectangular
Center-to-center distance	± 5 mm	Rectangular
Angular misalignment	$\pm 5^\circ$ (0.2% of K)	Normal
Center position misalignment	± 10 mm	Rectangular
Ground plane reflections	1% of F_a	Rectangular
Coupling equation approximation	0.4% of F_a	Normal
Magnetic field unevenness	0.5% of F_a	Rectangular
TX antenna current distribution	0.4% of F_a	Rectangular
VNA S_{21} measurement	0.6-1.0 dB	Normal, $k=2$

Table 4: Uncertainty budget for Three Antenna Method (TAM) calibration

- **Advantages:**
 - Absolute method requiring no reference standard
 - Direct traceability through VNA calibration
 - Suitable for both active and passive loop antennas
 - Frequency coverage 9 kHz to 30 MHz
- **Limitations:**
 - Requires three antennas of similar type
 - Low signal-to-noise ratio at lower frequencies (< 100 kHz)
 - Geometric alignment critical for accuracy
 - Ground plane effects contribute uncertainty

5.2.4 Reference Loop Antenna Method

This method calibrates an antenna under calibration using a reference loop antenna with previously determined AF . The method provides direct traceability to national standards through a single measurement, making it particularly suitable for active receiving loop antennas that may have different dynamic range requirements than passive loops. The magnetic AF is calculated using Eq. 47 where the coupling factor K is defined by Eq. 48 and R_0 by Eq. 49.

$$F_{aH}^{dB}(\text{AUC}) = -45.9 - 20\log_{10}(f_{\text{MHz}}) - S_{21}^{dB} + 20\log_{10}(K) - F_{aH}^{dB}(\text{STD}) \quad (47)$$

$$K = \frac{\sqrt{1+k^2R_0^2}}{2\pi R_0^3} \left[1 + \frac{15}{8} \frac{(r_{\text{STD}}r_{\text{AUC}})^2}{R_0^4} + \frac{315}{64} \frac{(r_{\text{STD}}r_{\text{AUC}})^4}{R_0^8} \right] \quad (48)$$

$$R_0 = \sqrt{d_{\text{STD,AUC}}^2 + r_{\text{STD}}^2 + r_{\text{AUC}}^2} \quad (49)$$

Measurement Setup

- Standard (reference) loop antenna connected to VNA Port 1 (transmitting)
- AUC loop antenna is connected to VNA Port 2 (receiving)
- Both antennas positioned above ground plane with aligned centres
- Height h , distance d , and alignment per CISPR 16-2-3 requirements
- Full 2-port VNA calibration performed

Uncertainty Contributions

The mathematical model typically includes uncertainty contributions as shown in Eq. 50.

$$F_{aH}^{dB}(\text{AUC}) = -45.9 - 20\log_{10}(f_{\text{MHz}}) - S_{21}^{dB} + 20\log_{10}(K) - F_{aH}^{dB}(\text{STD}) + k_{\text{mag}} + k_{\text{current}} + k_{\text{env}} \quad (50)$$

- k_{mag} uncertainty due to magnetic field unevenness
- k_{current} uncertainty due to TX antenna current distribution
- k_{env} uncertainty due to environmental reflections

Primary uncertainty sources:

1. **Reference antenna F_a :** Taken from calibration certificate (normal distribution, $k=2$)
2. **S_{21} measurement:** VNA measurement uncertainty (0.6-1.0 dB typical)
3. **Dimensional measurements:** Radius and distance (same as TAM)
4. **Magnetic field unevenness:** $\sim 0.5\%$ of F_a

5. **Current distribution:** $\sim 0.4\%$ of F_a
6. **Environmental effects:** $\sim 1\%$ of F_a (ground plane, reflections)

Combined standard uncertainty is typically between 1.3 and 2.0 dB ($k=2$), with higher uncertainties at lower frequencies due to noise contributions. The reference antenna uncertainty propagates directly into the AUC calibration.

- **Advantages**
 - Single measurement required
 - Direct traceability through reference antenna
 - Efficient for calibrating multiple antennas
 - Suitable for both active and passive loops
- **Limitations:**
 - Requires calibrated reference antenna
 - Reference uncertainty propagates to all calibrations
 - Low SNR at lower frequencies (< 100 kHz)
 - Geometric constraints must be satisfied

5.2.5 Helmholtz Coil Method

The Helmholtz coil method addresses the low signal-to-noise ratio problem at frequencies below 150 kHz where TAM and reference methods suffer from inadequate receiver sensitivity. Helmholtz coils generate a precisely calculable, uniform magnetic field in the centre region, providing excellent accuracy for validating other methods and calibrating low-sensitivity loop antennas. A Helmholtz coil consists of two identical circular coils separated by a distance equal to their radius, positioned coaxially. The axial magnetic field strength H_z in A/m at the centre is defined by Eq. 51. For ideal Helmholtz geometry where $r_1 = r_2 = r$, $N_1 = N_2 = N$, and $2a = r$, this simplifies to Eq. 52 where N is the number of turns per coil, I is the AC current through the coils, and r is the coil radius. The magnetic flux density is $B_z = \mu_0 H_z$, where $\mu_0 = 4 \cdot \pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ H/m.

$$H_z = \frac{8I}{\sqrt{125}r} \left[\frac{N}{\left(1 + \frac{r^2}{4a^2}\right)^{3/2}} \right] \quad (51)$$

$$H_z = \frac{8NI}{\sqrt{125}r} \quad (52)$$

Since loop antennas have finite size (b is antenna radius), the average magnetic field interacting with the antenna differs from the centre field. The magnetic flux through the antenna is defined by Eq. 53. For ideal Helmholtz geometry ($r = 2a$) Eq.53 simplify, Eq. 54.

$$\Phi_z = \mu_0 \frac{4\pi N I b^2}{\sqrt{(r^2 + a^2)^3}} \left[1 - \frac{3b^2(r^2 - 2a^2)}{4(r^2 + a^2)^2} \right] \quad (53)$$

$$\Phi_z = \mu_0 \frac{8\sqrt{5}\pi N I b^2}{25r^2} \left[1 - \frac{3b^2}{20r^2} \right] \quad (54)$$

The average magnetic field strength and flux density are defined by Eqs. 55 and 56 and the antenna factor F_a is calculated from the output voltage U_{out} (measured across 50 Ω load) using Eqs. 57 and 58.

$$H_{avg} = \frac{\Phi_z}{\mu_0 \pi b^2} \quad (55)$$

$$B_{avg} = \mu_0 H_{avg} \quad (56)$$

$$F_{aH} = \frac{H_{avg}}{U_{out}} \text{ [m}^{-1}\text{]} \quad (57)$$

$$F_{aB} = \frac{B_{avg}}{U_{out}} \text{ [T/V]} \quad (58)$$

Setup configuration:

Figure 20: Calibration setup for generating magnetic field with Helmholtz coil using function generator and audio amplifier

- Function generator → Audio/RF amplifier → Helmholtz coil + Ammeter (in series)
- Loop antenna positioned at centre of Helmholtz coil on Styrofoam holder
- Antenna output voltage measured with DMM (50 Ω termination) or oscilloscope
- Direct current measured by DMM or indirect measurement through precision shunt resistor (*e.g.*, 0.5 Ω) with DMM or oscilloscope

Dimensional measurements:

1. Measure coil radius r with calibrated ruler and Vernier calliper
2. Count number of turns N
3. Measure loop antenna radius b with calliper
4. Verify coil separation distance = $r/2$

Measurement procedure:

1. Set signal generator to desired frequency
2. Adjust amplifier output to achieve measurable antenna output voltage (typically 1-100 mV)
3. Measure current I through coil
4. Measure antenna output voltage U_{out}
5. Calculate H_{avg} using Eq. 27 and F_a using Eq. 29
6. Repeat at all calibration frequency points

Uncertainty Contributions

Uncertainty contributions are gathered in Table 5. Background field correction should be used for calibrations in the 45-55 Hz range by measuring background magnetic field (*i.e.*, coil current = 0) and include as uncertainty contribution or correction. Combined standard uncertainty is typically between 0.5 and 1.5 dB ($k=2$) in the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range and is significantly better than TAM at lower frequencies due to higher signal levels and reduced noise contribution.

Uncertainty Source	Typical Value	Distribution
Antenna output voltage (Type A)	0.5-2%	Normal
DMM resolution	± 0.5 LSD	Rectangular
DMM specification	Per certificate	Rectangular
Coil current (Type A)	Std dev of mean	Normal
Ammeter specification	Per certificate	Rectangular
Ammeter resolution	± 0.5 LSD	Rectangular
Coil radius r	± 1 mm	Rectangular
Antenna radius b	± 0.5 mm	Rectangular
Field inhomogeneity	1% of B -field	Rectangular
Holder presence (Styrofoam)	Negligible	—
Antenna insertion effect	0.5% of B -field	Rectangular
Background field (50 Hz)	By measurement	Rectangular
Permeability μ_0	Negligible	—

Table 5: Uncertainty budget for Helmholtz coil method

- **Advantages:**
 - Excellent accuracy at low frequencies (9 kHz - 150 kHz)
 - Calculable field from first principles (no reference antenna required)
 - High signal-to-noise ratio
 - Ideal for validating TAM and TEM cell methods
 - Suitable for passive antennas

- **Limitations:**
 - Frequency range limited to ~ 150 kHz (typically)
 - Antenna size constrained by coil dimensions (typically $b < r/3$)
 - Coil construction requires precision
 - Field inhomogeneity increases uncertainty for larger antennas
 - Not suitable for frequencies > 1 MHz due to coil inductance effects

5.2.6 TEM Cell Method

The Transverse Electromagnetic (TEM) cell, also known as Crawford cell, generates a uniform, calculable electromagnetic field between a septum plate and the cell body. This method provides wide frequency coverage (9 kHz to 30 MHz and beyond) and enables calibration with non-CW signals, making it the *gold standard* for loop antenna calibration according to CISPR 16-1-6 [4].

The TEM cell operates as a coaxial transmission line with a rectangular outer conductor and a flat septum (centre conductor). When RF power propagates through the cell, a transverse electromagnetic wave is established with calculable electric and magnetic field strengths. The magnetic field strength H in A/m in the TEM cell is defined by Eq. 59, where P denotes net power in the TEM cell (forward - reflected power) in watts, Z_0 is impedance of free space $\approx 377 \Omega$ and d is the septum height (distance between septum and cell floor), in meters. The magnetic flux density is defined by Eq. 60.

$$H = \sqrt{\frac{P}{Z_0 d^2}} \quad (59)$$

$$B = \mu_0 H = \mu_0 \sqrt{\frac{P}{Z_0 d^2}} \quad (60)$$

The antenna factor is calculated from the measured antenna output voltage U_{out} , Eqs. 61 and 62.

$$F_{aH} = \frac{H}{U_{out}} = \frac{1}{U_{out}} \sqrt{\frac{P}{Z_0 d^2}} \quad [\text{m}^{-1}] \quad (61)$$

$$F_{aB} = \frac{B}{U_{out}} = \frac{\mu_0}{U_{out}} \sqrt{\frac{P}{Z_0 d^2}} \quad [\text{T/V}] \quad (62)$$

Measurement Setup and Configurations

Fig. 21: Calibration setup for generating magnetic field strength in TEM cell

Configuration 1: Power sensor at output (low frequencies):

- Signal generator → RF amplifier → TEM cell Port 1
- TEM cell Port 2 → Attenuator → RF power sensor
- Loop antenna inside TEM cell → DMM or oscilloscope (50 Ω termination)
- Net power $P = (\text{power reading}) \times (\text{attenuator factor})$

Configuration 2: Directional coupler (higher frequencies):

- Signal generator → RF amplifier → Directional coupler → TEM cell Port 1
- TEM cell Port 2 → High-power 50 Ω termination
- Coupler forward/reverse ports → Power sensors (Net power $P = P_{forward} - P_{reverse}$)
- Loop antenna output → DMM/oscilloscope/power sensor (50 Ω)

Antenna positioning requirements:

- Loop antenna centered in TEM cell test volume
- Antenna plane perpendicular to magnetic field lines (parallel to septum)
- Maximum antenna size: 2/3 of septum height d (per CISPR 16-1-6)
- Mounted on low-permittivity holder (Styrofoam, $\epsilon_r \approx 1$, $\mu_r \approx 1$)

Uncertainty Contributions

Uncertainty contributions are shown in Table 6.

Uncertainty Source	Typical Contribution
Voltage Measurement	
DMM method: Type A, specification, resolution	0.1-0.5%
Oscilloscope: Type A, specification, resolution	0.5-1%
Power sensor (for loop antenna): Type-A, calibration factor, mismatch, attenuator	0.2-0.8%
Power Measurement	
Power sensor Type-A uncertainty	Std dev of mean
Power sensor calibration factor	Per certificate
Power sensor specification	Per certificate
Attenuator uncertainty	±0.1-0.3 dB
Mismatch (sensor-attenuator)	Per return loss
Coupler directivity (if used)	Typically 0.1-0.5 dB
Geometric and Field	
Septum distance d	±1-2 mm
Field inhomogeneity	1-3% (antenna size dependent)
Antenna insertion effect	0.5-1%
Holder presence effect	0.2-0.5%

Table 6: Uncertainty budget for TEM cell method

Combined standard uncertainty: Typically, 1.0-2.5 dB ($k=2$) over 9 kHz to 30 MHz range. Uncertainty increases for:

- Larger antennas approaching 2/3 septum height (field inhomogeneity)
- Lower frequencies < 100 kHz (power measurement challenges)
- Shielded loops at higher frequencies (10-30 MHz, potential resonances)

Key uncertainty drivers:

1. Net power measurement (dominant at low frequencies)
 2. Field inhomogeneity (dominant for large antennas)
 3. Antenna insertion effect and holder perturbation
 4. Septum distance measurement accuracy
- **Advantages:**
 - Wide frequency coverage (9 kHz to >100 MHz possible)
 - Calculable field strength from power measurement

- Suitable for non-CW signals (validation of saturation detection circuits)
- Single measurement required
- Good repeatability and reproducibility
- Recognized as *gold standard* in CISPR 16-1-6 [4]

- **Limitations:**

- Antenna size constrained (maximum 2/3 septum height)
- TEM cell acquisition cost and space requirements
- Field inhomogeneity increases for larger antennas
- Higher uncertainty than Helmholtz coil at very low frequencies

Comparison of Calibration Methods

Comparison of all four methods is given in Table 7.

Method	Freq. Range	Uncertainty ($k=2$)	Ref. std. required?	Antenna size limit
TAM	9 kHz - 30 MHz	0.6-1.0 dB (higher at low f)	No	Geometric constraints
Reference Antenna	9 kHz - 30 MHz	1.3-2.0 dB	Yes	Geometric constraints
Helmholtz Coil	9 kHz - 150 kHz (up to 1 MHz)	0.5-1.5 dB (best at low f)	No	$b < r/3$ typically
TEM Cell	9 kHz - > 30 MHz	1.0-2.5 dB	No	< 2/3 septum height

Table 7: Comparison of loop antenna calibration methods

Method selection guidance:

- **9-100 kHz:** Helmholtz coil preferred (best SNR and uncertainty)
- **100 kHz-30 MHz:** TEM cell or TAM (TEM cell for wide coverage, TAM for absolute calibration)
- **Validation:** Use Helmholtz to validate TEM cell at low frequencies
- **Active antennas:** All methods applicable; reference method most efficient for multiple units
- **Large antennas (>40 cm):** TAM or reference method (TEM cell size constraints)

5.2.7 Traceability Chain

Loop antenna calibration traceability is established through multiple measurement paths:

TAM and reference method:

- VNA calibration using certified calibration kit (open, short, load, thru)
- Calibration kit traceable to national metrology institute S-parameter standards
- Dimensional measurements (laser distance meter, callipers) traceable to length standards

- For reference method: reference antenna F_a traceable through prior TAM or Helmholtz calibration

Helmholtz coil method:

- Current measurement: Ammeter/shunt resistor calibrated against AC voltage/current standards
- Voltage measurement: DMM calibrated against AC voltage standards
- Dimensional measurements: Coil and antenna radii traceable to length standards

TEM cell method:

- RF power measurement: Power sensor calibrated against national power standards
- Attenuator/coupler calibration: S-parameter measurements traceable through VNA
- Voltage measurement: DMM/oscilloscope/power sensor with documented traceability
- Dimensional measurements: Septum distance traceable to length standards

5.2.8 Conclusions

Loop antenna calibration for EMC measurements in the 9 kHz to 30 MHz frequency range requires careful method selection based on antenna characteristics, frequency range, required uncertainty, and available facilities. The four primary methods—Three Antenna Method (TAM), reference antenna method, Helmholtz coil method, and TEM cell method—each offer distinct advantages for specific applications.

TAM provides absolute calibration without reference standards, achieving 0.6-1.0 dB uncertainty ($k=2$) but suffers from low signal-to-noise ratio below 100 kHz. The reference antenna method offers efficient calibration of multiple antennas with 1.3-2.0 dB uncertainty through a single measurement, ideal for production environments. The Helmholtz coil method is advanced at low frequencies (9-150 kHz or below) with 0.5-1.5 dB uncertainty and serves as an excellent validation tool for other methods. The TEM cell method, recognized as the *gold standard* in CISPR 16-1-6, provides wide frequency coverage (9 kHz to >30 MHz) with 1.0-2.5 dB uncertainty and unique capability for non-CW signal testing.

6. Antenna calibration on an OATS (30MHz-1GHz)

6.1 Antenna Calibrations in OATS in Accordance with ANSI C63.5, SAE ARP958 and CISPR 16-1-6 (30 MHz-1 GHz)

In order to perform antenna calibration using the Standard Site Method (SSM) in accordance with ANSI C63.5 [3], an Antenna Calibration Site (ACS) shall be used that demonstrates Normalized Site Attenuation (NSA) performance better than ± 1 dB. For antenna calibration in accordance with CISPR 16-1-6 [4], the antenna calibration site shall meet the Horizontal Polarization Site Insertion Loss (HP SIL) requirements. For calibration sites intended for use within CALTS, the Test Site Insertion loss (TSIL) shall be 1 dB or better.

According to ANSI C63.5 [3], antenna calibrations using the SSM method shall be performed at 3 m distance with ANSI C63.5:1988 [1] and 10 m distance with ANSI C63.5:2017 [3] using horizontal polarization (HP).

In this method, the configuration where the antennas are horizontally polarized and the distance between them (R) is 10 m will provide the best far-field antenna factors compared to all other configurations. In particular, horizontal polarization of the antennas will make the measurement less sensitive to field variations. For measurements below 1 GHz, the transmitter antenna height should preferably be selected at a sufficient height above the ground (h_1) of 2 m to eliminate unwanted parasitic effects from the metal ground. The receiver antenna is scanned between 1 m and 4 m during measurements to determine the maximum reception level. For measurements above 1 GHz, the height of all antennas above the ground is set to 2 m, the distance between antennas (R) is set to 3 m, and the polarization is set to horizontal polarization. For the receiver antenna, no additional scanning is required, and the height above the metal ground is set to 2 m.

The antennas are numbered as 1, 2 and 3; and three measurements are performed reciprocally.

Figure 22: Calibration method

Before or after the Antenna 1-2 / Antenna 1-3 / Antenna 2-3 measurements, a “normalization” measurement is performed to identify cable and connector faults. For this purpose, the receiver and transmitter antenna cables (with 10 dB or 6 dB attenuators) are connected using an N-type I connector.

Normalization, Antenna1-2, Antenna1-3 and Antenna2-3 measurements are completed, then the antenna factors are calculated. The following formulas are used to calculate the antenna factors.

Figure 23: Calibration setup

For ANSI C63.5 [3] Standard:

$$F_a(1) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,2} - A_{1,3} + A_{2,3} - K_D) \quad \text{dB}\left(\frac{1}{\text{m}}\right) \quad (63)$$

$$F_a(2) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,2} - A_{2,3} + A_{1,3} - K_D) \quad \text{dB}\left(\frac{1}{\text{m}}\right) \quad (64)$$

$$F_a(3) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,3} - A_{2,3} + A_{1,2} - K_D) \quad \text{dB}\left(\frac{1}{\text{m}}\right) \quad (65)$$

AN: Normalization measurement (dB)

A1,2: Antenna1-2 insertion loss measurement (dB)

A1,3: Antenna1-3 insertion loss measurement (dB)

A2,3: Antenna2-3 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$$K_D = 48.92 - 20 \cdot \log f_{\text{MHz}} - E_{\text{DH}}^{\text{Max}} \quad (\text{dB}) \quad (66)$$

$$E_{\text{DH}}^{\text{Max}} = \frac{\sqrt{49.2 \cdot \{d_2^2 + d_1^2 \cdot |\rho_h|^2 + 2 \cdot d_1 \cdot d_2 \cdot |\rho_h| \cdot \cos[\theta_h - \beta \cdot (d_2 - d_1)]\}}}{d_1 \cdot d_2} \quad \text{dB}(\mu\text{V}/\text{m}) \quad (67)$$

$$d_1 = [R^2 + (h_1 - h_2)^2]^{1/2} \quad (68)$$

$$d_2 = [R^2 + (h_1 + h_2)^2]^{1/2} \quad (69)$$

$$\rho_h = \frac{\sin \gamma - (K - j \cdot 60 \cdot \lambda \cdot \sigma \cdot \cos^2 \gamma)^{1/2}}{\sin \gamma + (K - j \cdot 60 \cdot \lambda \cdot \sigma \cdot \cos^2 \gamma)^{1/2}} \quad (70)$$

$$\gamma = \arctan \left(\frac{h_1 + h_2}{R} \right) \quad (71)$$

f_{MHz} : Frequency (MHz)

β : $2 \cdot \pi \cdot \lambda$

ϕ_h : Reflection coefficient phase angle

h_1 : Transmitter antenna height (m)

h_2 : Receiver antenna height (m)

R : Distance between antennas (m)

K : Ground base relative dielectric constant

σ : Ground base conductivity (S/m)

λ : Wavelength (m)

For CISPR 16-1-6 [4] Standard:

$$F_a(1) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,2} - A_{1,3} + A_{2,3} - K_{SSM}) \text{ dB} \left(\frac{1}{\text{m}} \right) \quad (72)$$

$$F_a(2) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,2} - A_{2,3} + A_{1,3} - K_{SSM}) \text{ dB} \left(\frac{1}{\text{m}} \right) \quad (73)$$

$$F_a(3) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,3} - A_{2,3} + A_{1,2} - K_{SSM}) \text{ dB} \left(\frac{1}{\text{m}} \right) \quad (74)$$

A_N : Normalization measurement (dB)

$A_{1,2}$: Antenna2-1 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$A_{1,3}$: Antenna3-1 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$A_{2,3}$: Antenna3-2 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$$K_{SSM} = 20 \cdot \log \frac{39.8}{f_{\text{MHz}}} - 20 \cdot \log [e_0(i, j) H_{\text{Max}}] \text{ dB}(\text{m}^2) \quad (75)$$

$$e_0(i, j) = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\left(1 + \frac{d^2 + (h_j - h_i)^2}{d^2 + (h_j + h_i)^2}\right)^2 - 2 \cdot \frac{d^2 + (h_j - h_i)^2}{d^2 + (h_j + h_i)^2} \cos \frac{2 \cdot \pi \cdot f_{\text{MHz}} \left(\sqrt{d^2 + (h_j + h_i)^2} - \sqrt{d^2 + (h_j - h_i)^2} \right)}{300}}}{\sqrt{d^2 + (h_j - h_i)^2}} \quad (76)$$

d : Distance (m)

h_i, h_j : Antenna heights (m)

f_{MHz} : Frequency (MHz)

Upon examining the above equations, it is also seen that the $E_{D_{\text{max}}}$ correction factor is used. The reason for using this factor is that the three antenna calibration methods are not performed in completely free space, but on a metal ground. Since all theoretical equations developed so far have been derived for completely free space, such a correction factor is necessary. These factors ($E_{D_{\text{max}}}$) have been theoretically calculated for each frequency and are presented as a table in the relevant standard (ANSI IEEE C63.5 [3]). When using the equations, the $E_{D_{\text{max}}}$ values must be obtained from these tables. When using the equations, the $E_{D_{\text{max}}}$ values must be obtained from these tables. Prior to starting the measurements, all measurement equipment shall be powered on and allowed to warm up for a sufficient period to ensure stable operation. The three antennas used for calibration shall be sequentially designated as Antenna 1-2-3. The measurement must be

configured such that Antenna 1 operates as the transmitting antenna and Antenna 2 operates as the receiving antenna. After setting the required measurement frequency on the signal generator and the receiver, the output amplitude of the signal generator shall be adjusted such that the signal level received at the receiver is at least 16 dB above the noise floor. The applied signal generator level shall be denoted as A1 applied and the signal level measured on the spectrum analyzer shall be recorded as A1 measured. Without changing the frequency or amplitude settings of the signal generator, the coaxial cables connected to both antennas shall be disconnected from the antennas and directly connected to each other. The difference between the signal generator output level and the level measured on the spectrum shall represent the loss of the measurement path and shall be denoted as A1 path. It shall be noted that A1 path represents the total system path contribution, including coaxial cables, fixed attenuators, any additional components in the RF path, such as preamplifiers. Although A1 path is generally considered a loss term, its value may become positive if RF amplifiers are present in the signal path. The procedure described shall be repeated for all required frequency points and frequencies should be based on the tables provided in ANSI IEEE C63.5 [3]. The same procedure shall then be applied with Antenna 1 operating as the transmitting antenna and Antenna 3 operating as the receiving antenna. Following the same steps, the intermediate value A2 shall be determined. Once the values A1, A2 and A3 have been obtained, the antenna factors of all three antennas shall be calculated using the equations defined for the three-antenna method.

Important points:

- Measurement settings shall not be changed between antenna measurement and normalization measurements.
- Cable connections should be handled carefully to ensure repeatability.
- Noise floor margins should be verified at each frequency.
- Any change in the RF signal path shall require repetition of the normalization measurement.

6.2 Uncertainties of the antenna calibrations

6.2.1 Defining Model Functions for OATS

For the calibration of biconical and similar antennas in the 30 MHz - 300 MHz frequency range under the ANSI C63.5 [3] standard:

$$UAF_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \{[(U_N + \delta_{M1}) - (U_{s12} + U_{s23} - U_{s13} + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_S + \delta_{DI} + \delta_{AN}) + \delta_C] - (\delta_H + \delta_D)\} \quad (77)$$

For the calibration of log-periodic, bilog, etc. antennas in the 30 MHz - 1000 MHz frequency range under the ANSI C63.5 [3] standard:

$$UAF_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \{[(U_N + \delta_{M1}) - (U_{s12} + U_{s23} - U_{s13} + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_S + \delta_{DI} + \delta_{PC} + \delta_{AN}) + \delta_C] - (\delta_H + \delta_D)\} \quad (78)$$

For the calibration of biconical and similar antennas in the 30 MHz to 300 MHz frequency range, in accordance with the CISPR 16-1-6 [4] standard:

$$UAF_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \{[(U_N + \delta_{M1}) - (U_{s12} + U_{s23} - U_{s13} + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_S + \delta_{DI} + \delta_{AN}) + \delta_C] - (\delta_H + \delta_D)\} \quad (79)$$

For the calibration of log-periodic, bilog, etc. antennas in the 30 MHz - 1000 MHz frequency range under the CISPR 16-1-6 [4] standard:

$$UAF_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \{[(U_N + \delta_{M1}) - (U_{s12} + U_{s23} - U_{s13} + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_S + \delta_{DI} + \delta_{PC} + \delta_{AN}) + \delta_C] - (\delta_H + \delta_D)\} \quad (80)$$

For the calibration of biconic and similar antennas in the 30 MHz - 300 MHz frequency range under the SAE ARP958 [6] standard:

$$UAF_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \{[(U_N + \delta_{M1}) - (U_{s12} + U_{s23} - U_{s13} + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_{DI} + \delta_H)] - (\delta_D)\} \quad (81)$$

6.3 Use of Fiber-optic Links

In order to minimize unwanted contributions, several requirements on the setup are imposed. When it comes to the cables there are restrictions both on how the cables are placed [1] as well as the use of ferrites [2]. This is done both to

minimize for the cables to interfere with the field as well as minimizing that cables pick up parasitic currents on its outer conductor. An alternative to using regular RF cables would be the use of Fiber-Optic Links (FOL). FOL's have the advantage of minimally affecting the field and that they are not susceptible to an incoming field in this frequency range

For a biconical antenna the fiber was tested both for the transmitter and the receiver side. The result is shown in Figure 24:

Figure 24: Result for the biconical antenna

Note that no conversion between NFSAF and FSAF has been made in either of the tests for the biconical antenna. This is a mathematical adjustment which does not affect the overall comparison between the different methods.

For an LPDA the result is shown in Figure 25:

Figure 25: SSM vs FOL calibrations for LPDA

And finally, the result for a hybrid antenna the result is shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26: SSM vs FOL results for the hybrid antenna

Tests show that it is fully possible to calibrate antennas using FOL's instead of traditional RF cabling when calibrating antennas on an OATS. This holds for the entire frequency range 30 MHz-1000 MHz and for different types of antennas. The powering of the FOL is preferred to be either using built-in batteries or that the power is supplied through the fiber itself to the unit in the mast. DC power cables are susceptible to picking up the signal between the antennas, distorting the result.

7. Calibrations in a FAR

7.1 Introduction

Calibration of antennas in the frequency range above 1 GHz is usually carried out in a fully anechoic chamber, a specialized shielded room designed to create an environment free of internal reflections and external electromagnetic interference. The walls, floor, and ceiling are covered with radio frequency (RF) absorbing materials that mimic "free space" conditions, ideally allowing electromagnetic waves to propagate without reflecting back to the device under test. The inner walls of the chamber are usually lined with pyramidal microwave absorbers. To extend the frequency band towards lower frequencies, it may be appropriate to complement these with ferrite tiles.

7.2 Instrumentation

Antenna measurements in an anechoic chamber can usually be performed using small signals, i.e. without amplifiers being necessary. In most cases, measurements are performed using a 50 Ω coaxial measurement system or waveguides. These measurements require an RF generator, power sensors, power meters, a three-port levelling device (either a directional coupler or a power splitter), coaxial cables and adapters.

Unless otherwise stated, antenna gain relates to the power of the travelling wave. Therefore, it is not necessary to use a four-port directional coupler to monitor the reflected power. However, if information about the reflected power is available, it can be used to calculate uncertainties due to impedance mismatch.

Alternatively, the transmission between the antennas can be measured directly using a vector network analyzer. However, high-quality cables must be selected and their movement minimised, since changes in attenuation can significantly impact measurement repeatability.

7.3 Three antenna method

This chapter discusses the use of the three-antenna method for calibration in a fully anechoic chamber while maintaining far-field conditions. The advantage of this method is that the gain of all three antennas can be unknown. If any of the antennas have already been characterised, they can be used to verify the results. However, measuring three pairs of antennas makes this method more laborious.

The basic measurement setup for the selected pair of antennas is shown in the following figure.

Figure 27: Diagram of the measuring setup

The antennas are positioned at a distance d that meets the far-field condition, i.e., when using standard horn antennas with an aperture diagonal D , the following applies:

$$d > \frac{2D^2}{\lambda}, \quad (82)$$

where λ is the wavelength in meters.

The distance d is usually 1 m or 3 m (measured from the edge of the aperture). At a distance of 1 m, especially for antennas with higher gain, energy exchange takes place in a relatively small volume, so the influence of the quality of more distant absorbers is less significant.

For transmission between the transmitting (T) and receiving (R) antennas, the following can be written:

$$G_T + G_R = P_R - P_T - 20 \log \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi d} \right) \quad (83)$$

G ... gain of the respective antenna (dB)

P ... measured power level (dBm).

The difference between the received power level P_R (dBm) and the power level on the transmitting side P_T (dBm) corresponds to the transmission coefficient S_{21} in dB. Since passive antennas are being considered, the system is reciprocal and therefore we consider $S_{21} = S_{12}$.

In general, for a pair of antennas (p, q) , the following applies:

$$g_{pq} = P_p - P_q - 20 \log \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi d_{pq}} \right) \quad (84)$$

where:

$$(p, q) = (1, 2); (2, 3); (3, 1)$$

Again, the system is reciprocal, i.e. (p, q) can be $(1, 2)$ or $(2, 1)$ and so on. Which antenna is transmitting and which is receiving is a matter of choice – in practice, mechanical arrangement, impedance matching, etc. are taken into account. Then, the following formula applies to the gain of individual antennas:

$$G_i = \frac{g_{ij} + g_{ki} - g_{jk}}{2} \quad (85)$$

$$(i, j, k) = (1, 2, 3); (2, 3, 1); (3, 1, 2)$$

7.3.1 Reducing the impact of multiple reflections

The following measures are recommended to minimise the impact of multiple reflections:

- The antenna pair is equipped with additional absorbers placed behind the antennas. This helps to suppress multiple reflections arising from the antenna apertures, as well as from auxiliary components (e.g. sensors and directional couplers) located behind the antennas.
- Furthermore, stepping is performed, which helps to average out the reflections to a certain extent.

Figure 18: Reducing the impact of multiple reflections by stepping

The step size Δd is chosen as a fraction of the wavelength, for example $\lambda/10$. Several steps are then performed, typically symmetrically around the nominal value of the measuring distance d . The obtained results are then averaged (see formulas below). When stepping, it is important to ensure that movement takes place in only one axis, with minimal angular deviation from the main axis.

$$g_{pq(n)} = P_{p(n)} - P_{q(n)} - 20 \log \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi(d_{pq} + n \cdot \Delta d)} \right) \quad (86)$$

$$g_{pq} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/2} g_{pq(n)} \quad (87)$$

7.3.2 Example of a measurement setup

An example of a measurement setup is shown in the figure below. Measurements are performed in a medium-sized anechoic chamber ($6 \times 4 \times 3.1$) m, where the interior space is naturally further reduced by ubiquitous 45 cm high

absorbers. The chamber shown is suitable for measurements in the range from approx. 1 GHz to approx. 50 GHz. The lower frequency is here influenced, among other things, by the absence of ferrite tiles.

Figure 29: Example of a measurement setup

7.3.3 Measurement uncertainty

The most common sources of uncertainty include the following:

A-type uncertainty

Measurement repeatability.

Power level measurement

Uncertainty of measurement by power sensors, influence of power meter resolution.

Mismatch error

Uncertainty caused by impedance mismatch between the antenna and the levelling three-port device, or between the antenna and the power sensor.

Distance between antennas

Uncertainty caused by an error in measuring the distance between the antennas.

Angle deviation

Uncertainty due to the antenna's angular deviation from the main axis.

Reflections inside chamber

Uncertainty due to reflections inside the chamber (multiple signal propagation, standing waves).

Levelling three-port device

Uncertainty due to power splitter asymmetry or uncertainty of directional coupler characterization.

Adapter insertion loss

Uncertainty caused by adapters properties.

7.4 Standard antenna method

The standard antenna method (SAM) method is one in which the unknown gain of a test antenna is measured by comparing it to an antenna with known gain. Ideally the test antenna is illuminated by a plane wave which is polarization matched to it, and the received power is measured into a matched load. The test antenna is then replaced by a gain standard, leaving all other conditions the same. The received power into its matched load is again measured. Now the gain of the test antenna can be calculated from the known gain of the standard antenna and the difference in received power at both measurements.

It is important that the standard antenna and the antenna under calibration (AUC) are placed at the same location. A roof mounted laser pointer can be used to advantage here.

The gain of the test antenna can be calculated as described in (88).

$$(G_T)_{dB} = (G_{ref})_{dB} + 10 \log \left(\frac{P_T}{P_{ref}} \right) \quad (88)$$

where:

$(G_T)_{dB}$ = Gain test antenna

$(G_{ref})_{dB}$ = Reference antenna gain

P_T = Received power when using test antenna

P_{ref} = Received power when using reference antenna

The antenna factor of the test antenna can be determined as

$$AF_{dB/m} = 20 \log(f_{MHz}) - (G_T)_{dB} - 29.79 \quad (89)$$

From (1) it can be seen that traceability requires that power, reference antenna gain, and varying positions when measuring reference/test antenna can be estimated in a traceable way.

Note on EMC Bilog antennas 1: On the bar of some Bilog antennas there is a mark telling where the antenna reference point is. This mark shall be used if nothing else is explicitly stated.

The cables should be dressed in such a way that they are influenced as little as possible from the incoming field. For the calibration of LPDA and hybrid antennas, the cable should be continuing straight back for at least 1m before dropping to vertical.

Figure 30: Setup for antenna calibration in anechoic chamber.

Figure 31. Test setup for antenna calibration in anechoic chamber.

Figure 32: Positioning of reference and test antennas. The rightmost antenna has a special reference point.

Figure 33: Example of correct cable assembly during calibration.

The far-field condition shall be satisfied for the test antenna. The distance to far-field for aperture like is defined as:

$$R \geq \frac{2D^2}{\lambda} \quad (90)$$

where R equals the distance, D is the largest dimension of any of the involved antennas and λ is the wavelength.

For a dipole antenna with length $l = \lambda/2$, the far-field would be:

$$R \geq \frac{2D^2}{\lambda} = \langle \text{Dipol} : D = l = \lambda/2 \rangle = \frac{\lambda}{2} \quad (91)$$

This is however a bit too small. Therefore, for electrically small antennas the condition $R > 3\lambda$ is recommended.

To improve accuracy, it is recommended that the calibration is performed twice: at two distances or, alternatively, two polarizations. Two polarizations are recommended be used for omni-directional antennas (e.g. dipoles), two distances otherwise. The change in distance shall be at least one quarter of a wavelength ($= 75/f_{\text{MHz}} [\text{cm}]$).

The requirement on the standard antenna(s) is that they i) need to have a gain that is already known with a small uncertainty and ii) be of a similar design, preferably of a make and model similar to the antenna being calibrated. For instance, a DRH antenna should be calibrated with the DRH antenna as standard. This can however be a bit impractical for a calibrations laboratory, as the numbers of standard antennas can grow quite fast. The major advantages of the standard antenna method is that if the standard antennas are sent to an NMI for calibrations, this will solve much of the traceability.

7.4.1 Measurement uncertainty

According to Friis transmission formula the free space field in front of a transmitting antenna can be expressed as:

$$(G_T)_{dB} + (G_{MT})_{dB} = 20 \log \left(\frac{4\pi R_T}{\lambda} \right) + 10 \log \left(\frac{P_T}{P_{MT}} \right) \quad (92)$$

$$(G_{ref})_{dB} + (G_{Mref})_{dB} = 20 \log \left(\frac{4\pi R_{ref}}{\lambda} \right) + 10 \log \left(\frac{P_{ref}}{P_{Mref}} \right) \quad (93)$$

where:

$(G_T)_{dB}$	= Test antenna gain
$(G_{ref})_{dB}$	= Reference antenna gain
$(G_{M,x})_{dB}$	= Receiving antenna gain. x = measurement 1 and 2.
R_T	= Distance receiving antenna and test antenna
R_{ref}	= Distance receiving antenna and reference antenna
λ	= Wavelength
P_{MT}	= Output power receiving antenna when the test antenna is measured.

P_{Mref} = Output power receiving antenna when the ref. antenna is measured.
 P_T = Received power by the test antenna.
 P_{ref} = Received power by the reference antenna.

(A1) and (A2) combined:

$$(G_T)_{dB} = (G_{ref})_{dB} + 10 \log \left(\frac{G_{Mref}}{G_{MT}} \right) + 20 \log \left(\frac{R_T}{R_{ref}} \right) + 10 \log \left(\frac{P_{Mref} \cdot P_T}{P_{MT} \cdot P_{ref}} \right) \quad (94)$$

(94) expressed linearly gives us the model equation for the error budget:

$$G_T = \frac{G_{ref} \cdot P_{Mref} \cdot P_T}{P_{MT} \cdot P_{ref}} \frac{G_{Mref}}{G_{MT}} \left(\frac{R_T}{R_{ref}} \right)^2 \delta(con.) \quad (95)$$

Below it is explained where the uncertainties of the components in (A4) are estimated:

- $G_{ref}, G_{Mref}, G_{MT}$ all causes variations in gain due to positioning accuracy.
- P_{Mref}, P_{MT} refers to variation in output power from the NA.
- P_T, P_{ref} are received powers at the two measurements. Relative power measurement.
- R_T / R_{ref} is the distance ratio. Division of distances “receiving antenna to test antenna” and “receiving antenna to reference antenna”.
- $\delta(con.)$ is the error due to disconnecting and connecting the cable to the antennas

Now the model equation (A4) results in the uncertainty budget in table A1. The sensitivity coefficients are from the partial derivatives of the model equation (eq. A4). It is to be noted that the measurement uncertainty is a relative uncertainty.

A typical measurement uncertainty budget consists of:

- A1 Uncertainty of the gain of the reference antennas
- A2 Uncertainty of the receiver antenna
- A3 Uncertainty of the NA (accuracy)
- A4 Uncertainty of the NA (temp drift)
- A5 Uncertainty from connecting and reconnecting the cables
- A6 Uncertainty in positioning.
- A7 Uncertainty from the preamplifier (if used, otherwise 0).
- A8 Uncertainty from phase center variations
- A9 Uncertainty from site imperfection

Number	Factor	Standard uncertainty	Distribution	Divisor	Sens. Coeff.	Contribution to std. uncertainty.
A1	G_{ref}	0.0715	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0412
A2	G_{MT}, G_{Mref}	0.0000	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0000
A3	P_T	0.0233	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0134
A3	P_{ref}	0.0233	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0134
A4	$A_i(T)$	0.0116	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0067
A5	$\delta(con.)$	0.0248	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0143
A6	ΔR	0.0067	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	2	0.0077
A7	$A_i(Amp.)$	0.0471	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0272
A8	A_{phase}	0.0715	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0413
A9	A_{site}	0.0715	Normal	1	1	0.0715
	G_T					0.114

Table 8: Uncertainty budget.

7.5 ANSI C63.5 (1–40 GHz), CISPR 16-1-6 (200 MHz – 18 GHz) and SAE ARP 958 (30 MHz-40 GHz) Standards for Antenna Calibrations in FAR and SAC

The antenna measurements configuration can be performed in Fig xxx based 3-antenna method. Antenna calibrations, with calculations in accordance with ANSI C63.5 [3] and CISPR 16-1-6 [4] can be performed in a Semi-Anechoic Chamber (SAC), with the floor covered with absorbing material. The selection of the test environment shall be based on the applicable standard and the required electromagnetic boundary conditions.

Figure 34: Antenna calibration setup in FAR

According to ANSI C63.5 [3], antenna calibrations in the frequency range 1 GHz to 40 GHz shall be performed using the Standard Site Method (SSM). A minimum of three antennas shall be used to perform the SSM calibration. One of these antennas shall be the antenna under calibration. Selections shall be arranged as mentioned in the above section.

To identify and compensate for errors introduced by coaxial cables and connectors, a normalization measurement shall be performed either before or after the calibration as mentioned previously. For the normalization measurement, the transmitting and receiving antenna cables shall be disconnected from the antennas. The cables shall be directly connected using an N-type female to female adapter. The normalization data shall be applied to all antenna calibration calculations. In accordance with ANSI C63.5 [3], three antennas shall be positioned at a height of at least 1.5 m above the ground plane. The ground surface beneath the antennas shall be covered with RF absorbing material. Antenna calibrations shall typically be performed at a 3 m separation distance using horizontal polarization (HP) or vertical polarization (VP), as specified by the standard.

For ANSI C63.5 [3] and SAE ARP958 [6] standards:

$$F_a(1) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,2} - A_{1,3} + A_{2,3} - K_D) \quad \text{dB}\left(\frac{1}{\text{m}}\right) \quad (96)$$

$$F_a(2) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,2} - A_{2,3} + A_{1,3} - K_D) \quad \text{dB}\left(\frac{1}{\text{m}}\right) \quad (97)$$

$$F_a(3) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,3} - A_{2,3} + A_{1,2} - K_D) \quad \text{dB}\left(\frac{1}{\text{m}}\right) \quad (98)$$

A_N : Normalization measurement (dB)

$A_{1,2}$: Antenna1-2 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$A_{1,3}$: Antenna1-3 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$A_{2,3}$: Antenna2-3 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$$K_D = 48.92 - 20 \cdot \log f_{\text{MHz}} - E_{\text{DH}}^{\text{Max}} \quad (\text{dB}) \quad (99)$$

$$E_D^{\text{Max}} = 16.9 - 20 \cdot \log R \quad \text{dB}(\mu\text{V}/\text{m}) \quad (100)$$

f_{MHz} : Frequency (MHz)

R : Distance (m)

For CISPR 16-1-6 [4] Standard:

$$F_a(1) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,2} - A_{1,3} + A_{2,3} - K_{SSM}) \text{ dB}\left(\frac{1}{m}\right) \quad (101)$$

$$F_a(2) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,2} - A_{2,3} + A_{1,3} - K_{SSM}) \text{ dB}\left(\frac{1}{m}\right) \quad (102)$$

$$F_a(3) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_N - A_{1,3} - A_{2,3} + A_{1,2} - K_{SSM}) \text{ dB}\left(\frac{1}{m}\right) \quad (103)$$

A_N : Normalization measurement (dB)

$A_{1,2}$: Antenna1-2 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$A_{1,3}$: Antenna1-3 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$A_{2,3}$: Antenna2-3 insertion loss measurement (dB)

$$K_{SSM} = 20 \cdot \log \frac{39.8}{f_{MHz}} - 20 \cdot \log[e_0(i, j)] \quad \text{dB}(m^2) \quad (104)$$

$$e_0(i, j) = \frac{1}{d} (1/m) \quad (105)$$

d : Distance between antennas (m)

h_i, h_j : Heights of the antenna i and antenna j (m)

f_{MHz} : Frequency (MHz)

There are a few details we need to pay attention to during this process:

- Antenna alignment and positioning should be verified prior to each measurement
- Absorber placement on the ground shall remain unchanged during the calibration sequence.
- Cable routing and mechanical stability should be controlled to ensure repeatability.
- Any cable and connector/adapters change in the measurement setup shall require repetition of the normalization measurement.
- For the CISPR 16-1-6 [4] standard, the height of the antennas above the ground (h_1, h_2) can be found in the standard's content.
- According to the SAE ARP 958 [6] standard, calibrations performed at a distance of 1 m can be carried out in the SAC without covering the ground with absorbent material.
- According to the SAE ARP 958 [6] standard, it is strongly recommended that biconical antenna calibrations be performed in the OATS.
- For 18 GHz- 40 GHz antenna calibrations, 6 dB should be used instead of 10 dB.

Gain values can be calculated from the antenna factor. The following equation is used for this purpose.

$$G_o (dB) = 20 \cdot \log f_{MHz} - AF (dB) - 29.79 \quad (106)$$

7.6 Three-Antenna Method in Accordance with the IEEE 149 Standard

Three measurements must be taken to determine the absolute gain of each antenna. In each measurement, a measurement is taken for one antenna pair. The antennas are named as "a", "b", and "c". Measurements shall be performed on the pair "a-b", "a-c", and "b-c", respectively.

Three equations will be obtained as a result of the measurements. The method described in this section is suitable for frequencies of 1 GHz and above in a laboratory environment.

Three antennas must be at least 2 meters above the metal ground, and the distance between them ensure far-field conditions. Furthermore, covering the metal ground between the antennas with electromagnetic absorber materials would be appropriate to reduce measurement uncertainty.

For (a-b) antenna pairs:

$$(G_a)_{dB} + (G_b)_{dB} = 20 \cdot \log\left(\frac{4\pi R}{\lambda}\right) + 10 \cdot \log\left(\frac{P_{rb}}{P_{ta}}\right) \tag{107}$$

For (a-c) antenna pairs:

$$(G_a)_{dB} + (G_c)_{dB} = 20 \cdot \log\left(\frac{4\pi R}{\lambda}\right) + 10 \cdot \log\left(\frac{P_{rc}}{P_{ta}}\right) \tag{108}$$

For (b-c) antenna pairs:

$$(G_b)_{dB} + (G_c)_{dB} = 20 \cdot \log\left(\frac{4\pi R}{\lambda}\right) + 10 \cdot \log\left(\frac{P_{rc}}{P_{tb}}\right) \tag{109}$$

The solution of these three equations is quite simple, but in order to solve them, the ratios of R , λ , $\left(\frac{P_{rb}}{P_{ta}}\right)$, $\left(\frac{P_{rc}}{P_{tb}}\right)$ must be known.

Figure 35: Calibration setup

The following point should be noted in the three-antenna methods:

- The system frequency should be stable.
- The antennas should meet far-field conditions.
- The antennas should be placed opposite each other in the direction of maximum directivity.
- All components should be compatible in terms of impedance and polarization.
- Environmental reflections should be minimized. Therefore, the process should be carried out sufficiently above ground level in a FAR/SAC or OATS.
- If the process is carried out in a SAC or on an OATS, covering the ground at least partially with absorbent materials will significantly reduce measurement uncertainty.

Let us briefly show how the stated equalities were derived.

- Antenna 1 : A_{em1}, G_{01}
- Antenna 2 : A_{em2}, G_{02}
- Antenna 3 : A_{em3}, G_{03}

The power density that Antenna 1 will create immediately above Antenna 2 for the measurement setup

$$W_{t1} = \frac{P_{t1}}{4\pi R^2} \cdot G_{01} \tag{110}$$

Here,

Wt1: Power density created by Antenna 1 on Antenna 2 (W/m²)

Pt1: Total power measured at the full input of Antenna 1 (will be radiated power for a lossless antenna) (W)

R: Distance between Antenna 1 and Antenna 2 (1 or 3 m)

G01: Gain value for Antenna 1 (equivalent to directivity for a lossless antenna) (dimensionless)
We can now find the power transferred by Antenna 1 to the load of Antenna 2 (50 Ω).

$$P_{r2} = W_{t1} \cdot A_{em2} = \frac{P_{t1}}{4\pi R^2} \cdot G_{01} \cdot A_{em2} \quad (111)$$

Here,

P_{r2} : Power level transferred to the load of Antenna (2) [W]
 A_{em2} : Maximum effective area of Antenna (2) [m²]

Hence, if we write the equation for the maximum gain and maximum effective area for Antenna 2, we get the equation:

$$A_{em2} = \frac{\lambda^2}{4\pi} \cdot G_{02} \quad (112)$$

Here,

λ = wavelength [m]

G_{02} = The gain of Antenna (2), equivalent to directivity for a lossless antenna and it has to be unitless.

Therefore, finally we can write,

$$P_{r2} = \frac{P_{t1}}{4\pi R^2} \cdot G_{01} \cdot G_{02} \frac{\lambda^2}{4\pi} \quad P_{r3} = \frac{P_{t1}}{4\pi R^2} \cdot G_{01} \cdot G_{03} \frac{\lambda^2}{4\pi} \quad (113)$$

Upon careful examination of these equations, we see that we have three equations with three unknowns. If we take logarithm of both sides and simplify them, we get,

For A-B combination:

$$(G_a)_{dB} + (G_b)_{dB} = 20 \cdot \log \frac{4\pi R}{\lambda} + 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rb}}{P_{ta}} \quad (114)$$

For A-C combination:

$$(G_a)_{dB} + (G_c)_{dB} = 20 \cdot \log \frac{4\pi R}{\lambda} + 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rc}}{P_{ta}} \quad (115)$$

For B-C combination:

$$(G_b)_{dB} + (G_c)_{dB} = 20 \cdot \log \frac{4\pi R}{\lambda} + 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rc}}{P_{tb}} \quad (116)$$

G_{01}, G_{02}, G_{03} the maximum gain values for Antenna 1, Antenna 2 and Antenna 3, respectively.

P_{ta}, P_{tb} : It is the power measured at the inputs of Antenna 1 and Antenna 2, respectively, and is known experimentally.

P_{rb}, P_{rc} : It is the power measured at the outputs of Antenna 2 and Antenna 3, respectively, and is known experimentally.

R is the distance between the antennas during the measurement and is known experimentally.

λ : wavelength and is known experimentally.

Solving all the equations up to this point will give us the maximum absolute gain values for the three antennas

Now we can write the solutions as,

$$G_a = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left[20 \cdot \log \frac{4\pi R}{\lambda} + 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rb}}{P_{ta}} + 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rc}}{P_{ta}} - 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rc}}{P_{tb}} \right] \quad (117)$$

$$G_b = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left[20 \cdot \log \frac{4\pi R}{\lambda} + 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rc}}{P_{tb}} + 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rb}}{P_{ta}} - 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rc}}{P_{ta}} \right] \quad (118)$$

$$G_c = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left[20 \cdot \log \frac{4\pi R}{\lambda} + 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rc}}{P_{ta}} + 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rc}}{P_{tb}} - 10 \cdot \log \frac{P_{rb}}{P_{ta}} \right] \quad (119)$$

Antenna factor at maximum gain value is,

$$G_o (dB) = 20 \cdot \log f_{MHz} - AF (dB) - 29.79 \quad (120)$$

7.7 Defining Model Functions for FAR/SAC

For the calibration of horn, log-periodic and similar antennas in the 200 MHz - 18 GHz frequency range, in accordance with the CISPR 16-1-6 [4] standard:

$$UAF_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot [(U_N + \delta_{M1}) - (U_{s12} + U_{s23} - U_{s13} + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_{DI} + \delta_{PC} + \delta_{NE}) - (\delta_H + \delta_D)] \quad (121)$$

For the calibration of horn, log-periodic and similar antennas in the 200 MHz - 1 GHz frequency range under the SAE ARP958 [6] standard:

$$UAF_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot [(U_N + \delta_{M1}) - (U_{s12} + U_{s23} - U_{s13} + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_{DI} + \delta_H + \delta_{NE}) - (\delta_D)] \quad (122)$$

For the calibration of horn, log-periodic and similar antennas in the 1 GHz - 18 GHz frequency range, in accordance with ANSI C63.5 [3] and SAE ARP958 [6] standards:

$$UAF_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot [(U_N + \delta_{M1}) - (U_{s12} + U_{s23} - U_{s13} + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_{DI} + \delta_H + \delta_{PC} + \delta_{NE}) - (\delta_D)] \quad (123)$$

For the calibration of horn, log-periodic and similar antennas in the 18 GHz - 40 GHz frequency range, in accordance with ANSI C63.5 [3] and SAE ARP958 [6] standards:

$$UAF_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot [(U_N + \delta_{M1}) - (U_{s12} + U_{s23} - U_{s13} + \delta_{M2} + \delta_{M3} + \delta_{DI} + \delta_H) - (\delta_D)] \quad (124)$$

Uncertainty components are given as:

Component Symbol	Component Name	Unit	Definition	Probability Distribution	Sensitivity Coefficient
U_{NA}	NA Accuracy-Normalization	dB	NA error arising from normalization measurement	Rectangular	1
U_{S12}	NA Accuracy-antenna (1-2)	dB	NA error arising from Antenna 1-2 measurement	Rectangular	1
U_{S13}	NA Accuracy-antenna (1-3)	dB	NA error arising from Antenna 1-3 measurement	Rectangular	1
U_{S23}	NA Accuracy-antenna (2-3)	dB	NA error arising from Antenna 2-3 measurement	Rectangular	1
δ_{M1}	Normalization impedance mismatch	dB	Impedance mismatch caused by normalization measurement	U-type	1
δ_{M2}	Port1-antenna impedance mismatch	dB	Impedance mismatch caused by the transmitter antenna during antenna measurements	U-type	1
δ_{M3}	Antenna-Port2 impedance mismatch	dB	Impedance mismatch caused by the receiver antenna during antenna measurements	U-type	1

δ_S	Site attenuation effect	dB	Error caused by SIL measurements of the reference OATS	Rectangular	1
δ_H	Height error	dB	Error caused by the height difference between antennas	Rectangular	1
δ_D	Distance error	dB	Distance error between antennas	Rectangular	1
δ_{Di}	Directivity error	dB	Error due to the alignment of the antennas with each other	Rectangular	1
δ_C	Cable attenuation variations	dB	Error due to cables during measurements	Rectangular	1
δ_{AN}	Environmental noise	dB	Error due to environmental noise during measurements in the OATS	Rectangular	1
δ_{Ref}	Ground reflection effect	dB	Error caused by reflections from the ground	Rectangular	1
δ_{PC}	Phase centre effect	dB	Error caused by changes in the phase centre of the antenna	Rectangular	1
δ_{NE}	Near-field effects	dB	Error caused by the antenna not meeting far-field conditions	Rectangular	1
δ_{Rep}	Repeatability	dB	Deviation of antenna factors obtained from measurements	Normal	1

Table 9: Measurement uncertainty

8. Definitions and abbreviations

- **Antenna Factor.** The antenna factor F_a is defined as:

$$F_a = E - V \quad (125)$$

Where V is the output voltage, in (dB μ V) from an antenna receiving a signal of field strength E , in (dB μ V/m)

- **ECSM.** Equivalent Capacitance Substitution method

- **FAR.** Fully Anechoic Room
- **FOL.** Fiber-Optic Link
- **OATS.** Outdoor Antenna Test Site
- **SAC.** Semi-Anechoic Chamber
- **VNA:** Vector Network Analyzer
- **DRH.** Dual Ridge Horn (antenna)

9. References

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